

Report D2.6 “Feedback Analysis Beta Release”

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Report D2.6

“Feedback Analysis Beta Release”

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Task	T2.1 Networking and Consultation
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Glossary of terms

<i>Item</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>TLO</i>	<p>Top Level Ontology.</p> <p>A top-level ontology is an ontology (in the sense used in information science) which consists of very general concepts (e.g., the concepts of object, property, relation) that are common across all domains.</p>
<i>MLO</i>	<p>Middle Level Ontology.</p> <p>Mid-level ontologies are primarily intended to extend and specialise the concepts of TLOs towards a set of specific disciplines with the aim of providing a core shared vocabulary for lower-level modules. A MLO will generally provide a higher level of detail than a TLO, extending the taxonomical structure of the ontology more along on the horizontal dimension (i.e., sibling classes under the same superclass).</p>
<i>DLO</i>	<p>Domain Level Ontology.</p> <p>Domain-level ontologies are further specialisations of MLOs, even closer to the application level. The vast majority of their concepts is related to a specific discipline/domain, with a few instrumental/pragmatic exceptions, and vertical connectors.</p>
<i>ALO</i>	<p>Application-level ontologies are further specialisations of DLOs, explicitly or implicitly hinged on a specific set of application cases. They usually include concepts related to a specific set of intended tasks rather than concepts related to a discipline per se.</p>
<i>TRO</i>	<p>Top Reference Ontology.</p>

	The top-reference-ontology is the upmost layer of the OCES, made up of a plurality of TLOs (i.e., BFO, DOLCE, EMMO) and the semantic alignment among them provided by T2.4 (the Meta-Ontology).
<i>BC</i>	<p>Bridge-Concept.</p> <p>One of the core tools developed by the Consortium in the context of T2.5. A Bridge-Concept is a stand-alone ontological entity cum template which acts as a mediator and a point of reference both for (vertical and horizontal) semantic alignments and with respect to widely employed domain knowledge resources such as standards (given a double Hub-and-Spoke structure).</p>
<i>OCES</i>	<p>OntoCommons EcoSystem.</p> <p>The network of interconnected ontologies currently being developed by OntoCommons Consortium. It includes a core of selected aligned TLOs (i.e., BFO, DOLCE, EMMO), MLOs and DLOs. In the course of the project further ontologies will be produced, according to specifications outlined by the Consortium, to achieve full coverage of the NMBP-39 area.</p>

Keywords

Feedback-Analysis, Networking, Experts-Consultation, OCES Beta Framework

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

The objective of D2.6 is to report on the WP2 activities on the collection and analysis of feedback, both internal (from members of the Consortium) and external (from external experts involved in Formal-Ontologies-related projects and stakeholders), regarding the OCES methodology and framework -for what chiefly concerns T2.4 & T2.5's proposals and efforts- at the current stage of development. The details on the main sources of feedback, the collection procedures, the analysis of said feedback and the final survey document are presented and commented.

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1. Introduction

The objective of D2.6 is to report on the WP2 activities (in the context of T2.1) related to the **collection and analysis of feedback** on the proposals and efforts of T2.4 & T2.5 (partly collected in D2.4 & D2.5), focusing on methodological aspects, tools and the overall framework. The analysis, conducted at different stages of advancement of the project, contributes to **(1)** ensuring the adherence of OntoCommons' direction to the needs and desiderata of an ever changing environment, and **(2)** improving WP2's outputs – avoiding possible negative effects due to echo chambers-effects, while at the same time **(3)** checking the degree of permeation of said outputs within the Consortium and the relevant communities.

A further -collateral- point concerns **(4)** the individuation of further effective ways to engage with stakeholders meaningfully and improve the feedback-adjustment loop.

As per (1) and (3), the task involves comparative aspects, requiring e.g., the extrapolation of stakeholders' needs and desiderata, and the analysis of similar (with respect to scope and goals) projects' theoretical assumptions, tools and overall approach to commonly identified problematic areas/cases.

In order to meet the points outlined above, feedback has to be collected from different groups and in different environments; as such, a **pluralistic methodology** for the collection and analysis of feedback, tailored to the specific situations, is unavoidable, and, in fact, arguably recommended.

Specifically -while in some situations a formal and mathematically-grounded approach to the collection (and analysis) of feedback would give more reliable results- semi-formal, informal or even indirect approaches can provide meaningful contributions to a successful completion of the task, whereas "success" should be understood on the basis of the capability of meeting the points outlined above.

Explicit feedback (being it rigidly constrained by a set of predefined options to certain questions, or consisting of "free comments") is just one of many possible sources, and possibly not the most trustable/helpful/actionable upon in each and every circumstance. **Implicit feedback** -such as the degree of penetration of specific jargon and its use-appropriateness of the feedback-providers- can sometimes offer insights which would otherwise be lost, though its evaluation might be complex and involve elements which are harder to pin down in a rigorous way.

This document is organized in the following way: in **§ 2** the main sources of feedback selected -and the criteria for the selection- are presented and exposed. Each of the **§§ from 2 to 7** is dedicated to the presentation of one of the emblematic events chosen as the focus of the report: specifically, **§§ x.1** offer a brief overview of the relevant event: its scope, its aims, and contextual information; **§§ x.2** examine the profile of the attendees (the **potential feedback-providers** for the given event), that being one of the most salient aspects for a correct and in-depth analysis of the feedback (as per the points above); **§§ x.3** touch on T2.4 & T2.5-related material exposed during the event, both to offer a further contextualisation of the received feedback and to fix the timeline from an operative point of view; in **§§ x.4** the specific methodology selected for the collection of feedback in the given event is described, and the underlying rationale for the choice expounded; finally, **§§ x.5** are dedicated to the feedback itself, and its in-depth analysis: the various aspects are considered separately before an overall picture is provided. The conclusions (**§ 8**) offer a general comment on the feedback received

throughout the various events, taking the timeline into due account. The discussion will touch on actions which have been taken, or will be taken, as a result of feedback, and consider possible derivative applications. Some considerations regarding **further feedback-gathering activities** will also be put forward.

2. Sources of Feedback

While -as per the introduction- the collection of feedback has been approached by WP2 as an **holistic activity not restricted to specific events or proposals/material**, this report has been organised **modularly**, to the end of improving reader accessibility. It was deemed that this approximation would provide an overall clearer picture of the feedback-loop and of the dialectic internal to the Consortium, as well as highlight synchronic discrepancies due to the involved feedback-providers' perspectives. To that end, a **chronological organisation of the material collected** in the task also appeared to be optimal.

As a result of the points above, it was decided to **focus on specific events which were major sources of feedback**, or in which new proposals and results from T2.4 & T2.5 were formally made available for the first time to the Consortium, or to the general public. Both internal and public events were included in the report - the former, to represent the **internal feedback-loop** and degree of permeation of the results in the Consortium; the latter, for **comparative purposes**, and, perhaps more importantly, to **evaluate the adherence of T2.4 & T2.5's material/proposals to stakeholders' desiderata**.

As a result of a retrospective evaluation of T2.4 & T2.5's latest developments, five core events were individuated: (1) the **"Top-Level and Mid-Level Multidisciplinary Workshop"**; (2) the **"FATLOS" Workshop**; (3) the **OntoCommons M18 – Consortium Meeting**; (4) **WP2's (latest) Internal Presentation**; (5) the **"FOMI22" Workshop**.

While more details will be provided in the sections dedicated to the specific events, in what follows the chronology and the reasons for the choices are briefly outlined:

<i>Event</i>	Date of the Event	Rationale for the Choice
<i>Top-Level and Mid-Level Multidisciplinary Workshop</i>	25/03/21; 29/03/21; 08/04/21; 24/05/21	The "Top-Level and Mid-Level Multidisciplinary Workshop" was a fundamental step for the activities of WP2 (and T2.4 & T2.5 specifically) to the end of guiding or helping to envision the organization of the other activities, as well as in setting up a first network of collaboration. In fact, the scope of the event was identifying and collecting input from existing stakeholders, at the same time searching for further resources through engagement with stakeholders. Among the event's outcomes, a first agreement on the methodology was reached. For its pivoting role, it is the first event we include and report in this deliverable.
<i>FATLOS: "discussion and Formalization of links Across Top-</i>	21/04/22	The "FATLOS" was a first formal presentation of preliminary results achieved in the context of the activities of T2.4 to salient figures in the world of Formal Ontologies. FATLOS focused on conceptual and technical aspects of the development of a Top Reference Ontology

<i>Level Ontologies</i>		(TRO), and discussed points related to the mapping methodology based on definitional extensions. The nature, formalization and limitations of these mappings were among the concerns that were addressed in the workshop. Relevant problems were individuated and discussed, both in order to find solutions salient for the project and to improve the state of the art of the discipline overall.
<i>OntoCommons M18 Consortium Meeting</i>	04/05/22 - 05/05/22	During "OntoCommons M18 – Consortium Meeting" the results of the cumulative efforts of T2.4 & T2.5 (and specifically those collected in D2.4 & D2.5) were exposed for the first time (at least formally) to the entirety of the OntoCommons Consortium. Specifically, (a) the methodology for the alignment of TLOs developed by T2.4 (and its first results with respect to the alignment of DOLCE and BFO), and (b) the pluralistic approach to the alignment of MLOs outlined by T2.5 were presented. The Consortium Meeting was an occasion for the collection of informal internal feedback, as well as second-hand feedback on stakeholders' desiderata – given other WPs' respective interactions with stakeholders.
<i>WP2's Internal Presentation</i>	13/07/22	The objective of "WP2's Internal Presentation" was to provide more information concerning Bridge-Concepts (one of the tools developed by T2.5, first presented in the context of the OntoCommons M18 – Consortium Meeting) to the OntoCommons Consortium, and to the members of WP3 specifically. Having Bridge-Concepts become one of the core tools for horizontal semantic alignments (at all levels), and, thus, for the establishment of an interconnected EcoSystem, collection of feedback regarding their receipt was deemed necessary. The internal presentation also aimed to reconfirm the adherence of the various tools, and of the approach overall, to stakeholders' needs and desiderata, as seen from the perspective of the members of the Consortium.
<i>FOMI22: "12th International Workshop on Formal Ontologies meet Industry"</i>	12/09/22 - 15/09/22	"FOMI" is a major event recurring annually in which -as per the label- the worlds of academia and industry meet to analyse and discuss opportunities and issues related to methods, theories, tools and applications based on formal ontologies. FOMI heavily contributes in setting up research agendas and in pushing forward industrial applications. As such, the event was deemed the perfect chance to present OntoCommons' methodological approach and results, both to the Consortium's industrial partners and to possible new applicants – and to receive their feedback. The event also allowed for a comparative analysis of OntoCommons' and other projects' trajectories.

3. Workshop: “Top-Level and Mid-Level Ontologies Multi-Disciplinary Workshop”

Figure 1 - TLO/MLO Workshop Banner

3.1 General Description of the Event

The **Top-Level and Mid-Level Ontologies Multi-Disciplinary Workshop** took place in three afternoon sessions from 14:00 to 18:30 on the 25th of March, 29th of March and 8th of April 2021, and with a final consensus meeting on the 24th of May with the workshop invited speakers as representatives for the community. It was organized as a joint effort by all WP2’s members, in the context of T2.1’s activities, and a more detailed exposition of organisation process and results can be found in D2.1.

The purpose of the event was to **present the OntoCommons project and gather existing experience and agreement on OCES’ overall methodological approach**. More concretely, the goal was to identify and collect input from existing stakeholders and search for further resources through a relevant stakeholder engagement activity. As per the DoA, the aim was to reach an agreement on the outlined methodology and the choice of the TLOs which would make up the first core of the TRO, while collecting suggestions (and declarations of interest) for the further extension of the TRO with other TLOs.

3.2 Attendee Profile

The workshop target audience spanned from the philosophical community to formal TLO/MLO developers and users. The heterogenous demographic, and the vast number of participants (207

registered for the workshop)¹ ensured a truly multi-disciplinary approach, taking into account different perspectives, and the representation of all the (categories of) stakeholders.

An analysis of the participants on the basis of their professional role (see figure 2) highlights a predominant participation by researchers, followed by scientists and engineers. Ontologists were only the 10% of the attendees. Arguably, many attendees could fit under different categories, and - the classification being by self-declaration- the results might be more telling of their preferred view of their professional persona and/or of the (perceived) relation between disciplines than of their actual form of engagement with formal ontologies (and relevant tools/applications).

Figure 2 - Participants by Profession

As for the attendees' Nationality, the participants were predominantly from European Countries, and specifically from Germany and Italy, followed by UK and Norway. From the American area, a strong representation of Brazilian stakeholders was observed, followed by a lesser -yet still relevant- participation from the USA (see figure 3).

The non-neutrality of the sample of potential feedback-providers with respect to Nationality arguably had no relevant impact on the results: from the point of view of needs and desiderata of stakeholders, the deviation should ensure that the OCEs methodology is tailored to stakeholders most likely to endorse the project; from the point of view of research and development, there is no significant data indicating the existence of geographically/culturally-specific echo-chambers in the field of formal ontology.

¹ A full list of the participants was made available in D2.1, §7.2, appendix 2.

Figure 3 - Participants by Country

3.3 Material Presented

The event took place in the early phases of the OntoCommons project. As a result of that, and in line with the event’s mission, the presentation of the OCES’ overall approach was juxtaposed with general relevant presentations on formal ontologies. Given the target audience, both technical, and non-technical, material was presented, with an attempt to cover different areas of interest for stakeholders.

Specifically, the contents of “TLO”, “MLO” and “tools” topics to be addressed during the workshop had been defined using WP1 first analysis of the existing stakeholders, taking also into account WP2 partners’ experience.² The topics were then assigned to selected experts.

The full details of the event organisation can be found in D2.1. Given the current purposes, a rough outline of the agenda shall suffice:³ the first day was devoted to the introduction of OntoCommons and its overall approach. The talk was delivered by Coordinators and the WP2 leader; Dr. Anne de Baas also provided an overview of the scope of the project as former EC Officer and organizer of past ontology-based events in Brussels within the European Commission.

The presentations made explicitly publicly available by the speakers were collected and included as an attachment to D2.1 – including the ones on OntoCommons’ approach, more relevant for this specific task.

Further points relevant specifically for the evaluation of the feedback are the following:

- making speakers aware of the scope of the workshop and the objectives of the OntoCommons project was deemed a key for the achievement of the workshop’s objectives.

² A [TLO survey](#) made by the [Digital Twin Hub](#) has been also considered.

³ See also figure 4 for a schematic representation of the agenda.

Speakers were exhorted to explicitly stress the importance of the pluralistic approach embraced by the project;

- one of the criteria used to select the invited speakers was their role in the community and their likely willingness to join further OntoCommons initiatives. The workshop had been designed from the beginning to attract potential stakeholders, proposing an opportunity for TLO/MLO developers and Experts to show the status of their activities to an audience interested into exploiting ontologies in their domain of interest. Such gathering was deemed suitable to the presentation of OntoCommons to a qualified audience (researchers, developers, and users);
- the selection of the experts to be invited was not done on the basis of their possible feedback contribution to the project; helpful feedback-providers were gathered as a by-product of the workshop's mission.

Top-Level and Mid-Level Ontologies Multi-Disciplinary Workshop AGENDA			
CET			
DAY 1			25 March 2021
14:00	5	Introduction	Welcome
14:05	15		Nadja Adamovic (TUWIEN)
14:20	5		OntoCommons Project Presentation and Objectives
14:25	15		Hedi Karray (ENIT)
14:40	15		Workshop Structure and Scope
			Emanuele Ghedini (UNIBO)
			OntoCommons: a Top Reference Ontology for TLOs/MLOs alignment
			Emanuele Ghedini (UNIBO)
			Ontologies and Interoperability in the NMBP Domain
			Anne de Baas
14:55	25	Lecture	What are and what role for TLOs?
			Stefano Borgo (CNR)
15:20	15	Break	
15:35	25	TLOs	GFO
			Heinrich Herre
16:00	25		Tupper-PSL
			Michael Gruninger
16:25	25		UFO
		Giancarlo Guizzardi	
16:50	25	YAMATO	
		Riichiro Mizoguchi	
17:15	25	OPM	
		Dov Dori	
17:40	20	MLOs	The Ontology of Time and Process
			Antony Galton
18:00			Conclusions Day 1
CEST			
DAY 2			29 March 2021
14:00	25	Lecture	Ontologies and Philosophy of Science
			Claudio Calosi
14:25	25	TLOs	BFO
			Barry Smith
14:50	25		DOLCE
			Claudio Masolo
15:15	25		EMMO
		Emanuele Ghedini	
15:40	25	BORO	
		Chris Partridge	
16:05	25	ISO15926	
		Matthew West	
16:30	15	Break	
16:45	20	MLOs	EMMO MLO
			Jesper Friis
17:05	20		Common Core Ontologies
			Ron Rudnicki
17:25	20	AFO	
		Heiner Oberkamp	
17:45	20	IOF Core Ontology	
		Chris Will	
18:05	20	TLOs	SIO
			Michel Dumontier
18:25			Conclusions Day 2
CEST			
DAY 3			8 April 2021
14:00	20	EXPERTS	HETS
			Till Mossakowski
14:20	20		Matching top and domain ontologies
			Cassia Trojan
14:40	20		Ontology Design Patterns
			Aldo Gangemi
15:00	20	Digital Marketplaces/Simulation Platforms	
		Adham Hashibon	
15:20	20	ISO/TC 184/SC 4 "Industrial data"	
		Nils Sandmark	
15:40	20	The Upper Ontology Alignment Tool	
		Pascal Hitzler	
16:00	15	Break	
16:15	15		Future Events
16:30	45		Survey Results and Discussion
17:15	45		OntoTrans Project Feedback
18:00			End Of Workshop

Figure 4 - Workshop Agenda

3.4 Feedback Collection: Methodology

The methodology to collect feedback and gather agreement has been widely discussed within WP2 in the first months of the OntoCommons project. Ultimately, it was decided to (1) present the attendees with a **questionnaire**, acting as a **survey**, before the event had taken place, as well as to (2) collect feedback informally in the course of the workshop (from the discussion).

It should be noted that the questionnaire was also aimed at collecting preliminary information to help the organizers to better address the topics that were to be discussed during the workshop. The complete text of the survey is available *infra*, whereas the complete (anonymous) survey results are provided in the attachments to D2.1. A total of 40 complete questionnaires had been collected during the event.

The definition of the areas of interest for the relevant stakeholders (“TLO”, “MLO”, “tools”) had the further purpose of serving as a guide for the organisation of the survey, which in turn provided hints for the analysis of the feedback (both formal and informal).

The decision to avoid presenting the attendees with a second survey (after the event had taken place) was taken not to abuse of their time and availability, privileging their willingness to further engage actively with the Project (and actively take part in feedback collection activities) on the collection of more feedback.

While a post-event survey was considered, it has been decided that the best option to exploit the positive involvement of experts during the workshop was to actively involve them in further face-to-face or online events instead of asking them to report their ideas in a further questionnaire.

3.4.1 Survey Specifics

The questionnaire presented to the feedback-providers included a glossary of terms and 32 questions. While no reminder of the anonymity of the questionnaire was provided within the latter, said information was explicitly delivered via the invitation e-mail.

The glossary served to avoid confusions regarding the acronyms. Providing definitions for the hierarchical classification of ontologies was also deemed necessary to avoid ambiguities and improve the overall quality of the feedback.

Of the 32 macro-questions, 15 were rigidly constrained by a set of predefined options (of which, 12 required to express a degree of agreement with a statement in a graded range [0-10]; 3 required to express a degree of relevance for a set of characteristics given a graded range [0-4]); 17 were open questions (15 asked for a “free comment” on the expressed preferences; 2 asked more complex questions, allowing an higher degree of freedom).

The choice of the grading system took into account the possibility of expressing a “neutral” evaluation, as a means of getting more relevant feedback. The use of rigidly constrained options allowed for a faster short-term analysis of the data, in line with the scope of the workshop, at the same time ensuring that some explicit feedback would be available for analysis.

The hypothetical time to fully compile the questionnaire was taken into account, considering the assumed degree of availability of the relevant feedback-providers (as per the discussion above).

04/11/21, 23:33

Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

The questionnaire is aimed to collect preliminary information that will help organizers to address the topic that will be discussed during the workshop and to prepare the final workshop report.

* Required

Definitions

A Top Level Ontology (TLO) provides a formal characterization of general concepts according to specific ontological perspectives, providing basic relations and conceptual framework for lower, more detailed, ontology modules.

Middle Level Ontologies (MLOs) extend TLO concepts towards a specific discipline (e.g. manufacturing, materials science, chemistry) with the aim to provide a core shared vocabulary for lower level modules. A MLO will provide a higher level of detail than a TLO, extending the taxonomical structure of the ontology more along on the horizontal dimension.

A Domain Level Ontology (DLO) targets a specific domain of applications (e.g. additive manufacturing, composite materials). A DLO is characterized by an increased level of detail with respect to an MLO, a more pronounced horizontal extension and a strong dependency on the domain of application, while still maintaining some neutrality with respect to the specific problem addressed.

An Application Level Ontology (ALO) is aimed to represent specific application cases (e.g. a device from a specific manufacturer) with highly specialized classes and individuals.

1. An ontology should always refer to a Top Level Ontology. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

2. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

3. A TLO greatly facilitates the development of ontologies in general. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

04/11/21, 23:33

Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

4. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

5. TLOs are difficult to understand since they refer to terms and concepts not clearly understandable by people working on the application fields. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

6. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

7. A clear philosophical commitment (e.g. realism, nominalism) is important for a TLO. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

8. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

9. There is not a single TLO which is valid for all purposes, since there are more ways to express general concepts depending on the ontologist perspective. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

10. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

04/11/21, 23:33

Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

11. I prefer to stick on the conceptualization/axiomatization developed ad hoc for my approach than changing my perspective adopting a more general TLO/MLO. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

12. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

13. Adoption of common TLO/MLO greatly enhances interoperability between ontologies. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

14. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

15. In the trade off between expressivity (e.g. FOL vs RDF) and tractability (e.g. undecidability vs decidability, computational efficiency) I prefer tractability. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

16. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1wotNuoJX5-VKZoRAyiT3piU_TzEXAvZIEVNz-eNjB2g/edit

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Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

17. The ability to infer new statements from given knowledge is the most important feature for a TLO/MLO. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

18. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

19. A good documentation is paramount for the effective use of a TLO/MLO as a basis for DLO. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

20. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

21. A MLO should be defined according to the discipline of interest (e.g. chemistry) instead of according to its formal structure (e.g. taxonomy class levels) *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

22. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1wt1NuoJX5-VKZoRAyiT3piU_TzEXAvZIEVNz-eNjB2g/edit

4/6

04/11/21, 23:33

Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

23. The choice of an ontology for my application is driven by the requirements/limitations of the tools I'm planning to use or that are available to me. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

24. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

25. Quantify the relevance of each of the following ontology levels in practical applications: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	0 (not relevant)	1	2	3	4 (highly relevant)
Top Level Ontologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Mid Level Ontologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Domain Level Ontologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Application Level Ontologies	<input type="radio"/>				

26. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

27. There is lack of tools or need for further developments in order to enable or facilitate the TLO/MLO development and usage in practice *

Mark only one oval per row.

	0 (not relevant)	1	2	3	4 (highly relevant)
Editors	<input type="radio"/>				
Reasoners	<input type="radio"/>				
Provers	<input type="radio"/>				
Visualization	<input type="radio"/>				
Optimization	<input type="radio"/>				

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1wotNuoJX5-VKZoRAyiT3piU_TzEXAvZIEVNz-eNjB2g/edit

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Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

28. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

29. Which language do you prefer for TLO/MLO development/usage: *

Mark only one oval.

HOL

FOL

OWL

RDFS

Other: _____

30. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

31. What are the bottlenecks or unresolved issues that are actually preventing or slowing the use of ontologies in Europe scientific and industrial landscape? *

32. What are the unexploited capabilities of ontologies that could contribute to the digitalisation of scientific and industrial sectors? *

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Google Forms

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1wt1NuojX5-VKZoRAyiT3piU_TzEXAvZIEVNz-eNjb2g/edit

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3.5 Feedback Analysis

3.5.1 Analysis of the Survey's Results

The results of the questionnaire were presented during the third workshop day. The following tables offer a schematic report of the average numerical value relative to the questions which could be object of mathematical treatment, together with the standard deviation. Notes on the related open comments, and the analysis of the two considered together, are offered in the third column.

<i>Question/Statement</i>	Average Value and Standard Deviation	Notes & Analysis
<i>"An ontology should always refer to a Top Level Ontology"</i>	6,69/10 ⁴ (σ 2.81)	"Always" was perceived as too strong a commitment by many feedback-providers, though the general point was accepted. Likewise "refer" in some cases was understood as "be based on", and it was pointed out that the connection can be established afterwards. Such points might have influenced the grading, though an autonomous correction by some feedback-providers based on principles of charity should be expected (the -comparatively-high standard deviation can also be evaluated in that light).
<i>"A TLO greatly facilitates the development of ontologies in general"</i>	7,58/10 (σ 2.02)	The free comments tended to focus on the importance of having a defined theoretical background to rely on, and push the boundaries of the question towards interoperability. Some feedback-providers lamented the difficulties in connecting to TLOs (and -even more so- to a multiplicity of them).
<i>"TLOs are difficult to understand since they refer to terms and concepts not clearly understandable by people working on the application fields"</i>	6,42/10 (σ 2.35)	Despite the strong formulation of this statement (which -given the free comments-might have been perceived as charging people working on the application fields for their inability to understand certain terms and concepts) the average is relatively high.
<i>"A clear philosophical commitment (e.g. realism, nominalism) is important for a TLO"</i>	6,42/10 (σ 2.83)	In some of the comments the consistency of the background theoretical assumptions and of the ontology (qua logical system) were seen as going hand-in-hand. That might have influenced the high average (as well as the high standard deviation). Some feedback-providers

⁴ It ought to be reminded that the range in this case is [0,10]; the "neutral value" is 5/10.

		reported their inability to understand the question.
<i>"There is not a single TLO which is valid for all purposes, since there are more ways to express general concepts depending on the ontological perspective"</i>	7,39/10 (σ 2.58)	Placing this question after one related to philosophical commitments might have resulted in unexpected effects: a tendency for abstractness was observed in the free comments, with a focus on the discussion of ideal scenarios. Nevertheless, the average is definitely high, marking an openness to pluralistic solutions (at least pragmatically) even before the workshop had taken place.
<i>"I prefer to stick to the conceptualization/axiomatization developed ad hoc for my approach than changing my perspective adopting a more general TLO/MLO"</i>	3,61/10 (σ 2.88)	This question was targeted at a particular group of feedback-providers, so the results might have been influenced by the samples' heterogeneity (see the standard deviation). Given the free comments, the statements seem to have been considered "in principle", rather than focusing on personal experience (when applicable).
<i>"Adoption of common TLO/MLO greatly enhances interoperability between ontologies"</i>	8,61/10 (σ 2.07)	It should be noted that that statement was expressed in a strong fashion. The high average serves to demonstrate the feedback-providers' knowledge of the relevant literature, with some of the comments reinforcing an analysis to the end that that the agreement is not simply based on blind faith and lack of caution.
<i>"In the trade-off between expressivity (e.g. FOL vs RDF) and tractability (e.g. undecidability vs decidability, computational efficacy) I prefer tractability"</i>	4,75/10 (σ 2.62)	Despite the possible lack of clarity in the question's formulation, the free comments show that there was no impediment to its understanding. The results were not as polarizing as it might have prima facie been expected, and tend to favour expressivity, despite the (alleged) low number (ratio-wise) of ontologists present at the workshop (but compare with §3.2). Interestingly, the free comments did not emphasize a clash between theoretical and practical desiderata (ideal scenarios and pragmatic necessities), as much as the existence of different perspectives, possible depending on the level of focus.
<i>"The ability to infer new statements from given knowledge is the most important feature for a TLO/MLO"</i>	5,53/10 (σ 2.34)	A strong statement was chosen on purpose, yet some of the answers highlighted how the focus on TLOs/MLOs might have skewed the data. The comments seemed to suggest that lower level ontologies benefit more from the possibility of interoperability than from the added reasoning. In lights of that, the matter was deemed as requiring further investigation.

<i>"A good documentation is paramount for the effective use of a TLO/MLO as a basis for DLO"</i>	8,78/10 (σ 2.21)	Once again, a strong formulation of the statement was chosen on purpose. Arguably, given the free comments, the result can be taken at face value.
<i>"A MLO should be defined according to the discipline of interest (e.g. chemistry) instead of according to its formal structure (e.g. taxonomy class levels)"</i>	6,64/10 (σ 2.27)	This question served as a way to better contextualize the other answers, clarifying how the feedback-provider understood "MLO", yet the free comments seem to put the reliability of the extrapolation process into question.
<i>"The choice of an ontology for my application is driven by the requirements/limitations of the tools I'm planning to use or that are available to me"</i>	4,92/10 (σ 3,10)	"Driven" was understood in different ways, leading to vastly different answers, as it is reflected by the high standard deviation. That can also serve to explain the closeness to the "neutral value".
<i>"Quantify the level of the following ontology level in practical applications: TLO"</i>	2,31/4 (σ 1,37)	The standard deviation is fairly significant given the range.
<i>"Quantify the level of the following ontology level in practical applications: MLO"</i>	2,61/4 (σ 1,06)	
<i>"Quantify the level of the following ontology level in practical applications: DLO"</i>	3,44/4 (σ 0,72)	
<i>"Quantify the level of the following ontology level in practical applications: ALO"</i>	2,50/4 (σ 0,65)	
<i>"There is a lack of tools (editors) or need for further developments in order to facilitate the TLO/MLO development and usage in practice"</i>	2,97/4 (σ 1,01)	
<i>"There is a lack of tools (reasoners) or need for further developments in order to facilitate the TLO/MLO development and usage in practice"</i>	2,69/4 (σ 0,99)	
<i>"There is a lack of tools (provers) or need for further developments in order to facilitate the TLO/MLO development and usage in practice"</i>	2,53/4 (σ 1,14)	

<i>development and usage in practice"</i>		
<i>"There is a lack of tools (visualization) or need for further developments in order to facilitate the TLO/MLO development and usage in practice"</i>	3,06/4 (σ 1,03)	
<i>"There is a lack of tools (optimization) or need for further developments in order to facilitate the TLO/MLO development and usage in practice"</i>	2,94/4 (σ 0,94)	

The following figures present a collection of salient answers to the last two open questions:

Workshop Scope II

What are the bottlenecks or unresolved issues that are actually preventing or slowing the use of ontologies in Europe scientific and industrial landscape?

Tools

Too many competing TLOs, which one to use? Too many silos at domain-level, not often willing to share or make interoperable

The **battles between owners of different ontologies** seem to hamper progress and adoption. These owners should acknowledge the need to harmonise and realise this does not mean they "loose" or "become invisible". A harmonised ecosystem will create trust in industry. Standardisation should not be the first goal but should grow over time.

A main bottleneck is **competence**. There is a lack of people that are able to write good and reusable ontologies.

Lack of good tooling and eco-systems that makes it easy and efficient to map existing data sources to ontological concepts is greatly slowing down the development.

Lack of interoperability

Clear communication, which problem classes can be solved with ontologies and even more, which problems can't be solved with ontologies. **Education and training. Incentives** for using ontologies in the scientific community.

To demonstrate and prove that ontologies allow us to **build a better information system** and will help in the decision make process.

I think there is **not enough knowledge on how to develop and use ontologies in the field**, in industry.

In industry, particularly in the engineering area, there is almost **no information about the possibility to use ontologies**. EMMC is starting to provide a good path on materials, but it is on a very limited area.

Workshop Scope II

What are the unexploited capabilities of ontologies that could contribute to the digitalisation of scientific and industrial sectors?

Data documentation

My motivation for using ontologies is to **enable computers to more accurately match knowledge "needs" and "seeds"** (finding the "diamond in the rough"). The goal is to match a knowledge seeker with a knowledge provider that the seeker does not know but should know. To do this, we need descriptors for human knowledge that are "understandable" by computers. I believe that logical reasoning based on DL Ontologies (with support from rules) is the most effective way to approach this.

Linking data from various sources

Expression of well established technical standards (ISO, DIN, BS, ...) as ontologies and linked data.

In many areas, ontologies could help with **standardisation of terminology**, with data integration etc. management / representation / classification of **big data**

Using the ontology graph to do implement **workflow reasoning, ML/AI deductions and autonomy**.

I think **model-based development is unfortunately rare in application and system development**. My interest there is what led me to ontologies. The appeal of model-based development is that it leads to designs and implementation that are well aligned with the domain in which reasoning and software are applied. And that makes them more resilient to change.

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As a result of the analysis of the questionnaire, and for the sake of their exposition, during the third day of the event, a monologue -from the point of view an ideal average feedback-provider- was put together, based on the scores shown above.

Being, arguably, an emblematic representation of the feedback provided in the survey, the monologue is reported here in what follows:

"I **would** really like for **every ontology to refer to a TLO**, since they for sure facilitate the development of specific ontologies and **greatly enhance interoperability**. However, TLO are sometimes **not clearly understandable by non-expert** people working on the application field, that are only **partially interested on the philosophical commitment** of the TLO, if it works for them. By the way, it's almost an **absolute truth that a good documentation** is the priority for a TLO!

It is also quite evident that there is **not a single TLO valid for each application domain**, that's why I'm looking forward to having some **bridging between ontologies**. Also **reusing work done within existing disciplines** should be the way for **MLO** definition and development, instead of starting from scratch from the top.

I know there is a trade-off between **expressivity and tractability**, but it should be solved **depending on the application case**, with TLOs providing **scalable expressivity versions to be chosen by the users**. The same holds for **reasoning, that may be useful to in the AI field but generally not always used**. From an application perspective, the **tools** often impose constraints to the choice of ontology expressivity, but this may not be the case for a theoretical ontologist.

I feel a **lack of tools**, especially **editors, visualizers, and optimizers**, and of **competences in the education** of potential users, scientific communities, and industry. Another bottleneck is the

competition between TLO that may create **ontological silos** that jeopardize the overall TLOs efforts, and that can be overcome by clear communication and documentation.”

3.5.2 Holistic Analysis of the Explicit Feedback

Both formal and informal feedback were object of discussion and analysis in the consensus meeting held by UNIBO (on the platform: Teams) on the 24th of May 2021. A total of 19 attendees were present, including WP2 partners and workshop speakers, to ensure a neutral and pluralistic evaluation of the results:

- Emanuele Ghedini
- Anne Franciska de Baas
- Guizzardi Giancarlo
- Matthew West
- Jesper Friis
- Chris Partridge
- Stefano Borgo
- Mohamedhedi Karray
- Claudio Masolo
- Gerhard Goldbeck
- Adham Hashibon
- Arkopaul, Sarkar
- Dimitrios Kyritsis
- Dov Dori
- Nils Sandsmark
- Emilio Sanfilippo
- Riichiro Mizoguchi
- Michael Gruninger
- Aldo Gangemi

The meeting defined a set of sentences summarizing the workshop outcomes, and reached consensus, which is reported in what follows:

Workshop Outcome Summary and Proposed Strategies

1. **Referring to a common TLO within an organization, community or project** or a framework of mapped TLOs for the development of a domain specific ontology (MLO, DLO or ALO) **facilitates its development** and **greatly enhances interoperability** between ontologies.

TLOs⁵ should provide a sound theoretical foundation of consistent and well-defined logical theories and interpretation frameworks that should fit the needs of large communities of users, saving the time and cost for the from scratch development and the requirements of specific skills (e.g., conceptual and ontology engineering, logics) that are not actually be available within each specific community.

However, the overhead of introducing a TLO may not be justified in all application cases (e.g., small projects) and partial or no TLO adoption could be the fastest and cheapest approach. We suggest that initiatives with a large scope and ambition funded by public institutions (such as Horizon Europe initiatives, or European national initiatives) or large companies, should adopt an organization wide TLO approach and a TLO based framework like the one proposed by OntoCommons. In this sense, demonstrators may play an important role in showing the capabilities and limits of TLO.

2. There is a **disciplinary barrier** towards the adoption of TLOs, since they refer to **terms and concepts coming from the ontology or philosophy vocabulary** that are **often obscure to people working in a specific application field**. Therefore, the TLO terms and concepts should be accessible and understandable to users.

TLOs can be a barrier for some people since domain experts seldom grasp TLOs approach and architecture, and in many cases is the reason why they are not used. MLO and DLO are easier to understand by non-ontology experts that usually refer directly to them.

A well-defined and accurate adoption route (e.g., dedicated training courses and educational paths), together with good documentation should be the priority for a TLO to overcome some of these barriers.

3. There may be multiple TLOs suitable to represent any application. For this reason, **it is not expected, nor is reasonably feasible to assume that a single specific TLO will be chosen by all the communities**. A bridging between TLOs seems possible and is needed to retain a community preferred approach and at the same time provide ways to share knowledge with other communities.

There are many TLOs, expressions of different communities, often with conflicting commitments, so that there isn't a one-size fits all approach. A single ontology might be a philosophical ideal, but it is almost certainly not a practical reality and the use of many different TLOs in practice is a

⁵ TLO = Top Level Ontology, MLO = Mid-Level Ontology, DLO = Domain Level Ontology, ALO = Application-Level Ontology

reality that cannot be neglected, nor removed. There should be a trade-off between a generic TLOs pluralism and the focus on single approaches to be found within each specific area of interest.

A scalable approach to alignment between different ontologies (from syntactical to terminological and finally conceptual, depending on the specific application case), is the suggested route to deal with such *de facto* pluralism, as proposed by OntoCommons.

4. There is a strong difference in the approaches and objectives **while going from pure ontologists to application domain users**.
 - a. Languages: ontologies need to exist in different representations that address different (and sometimes incompatible) requirements. Amongst the objectives, some of these representations will optimize expressivity (which are important to some communities and applications), others will optimize computational performance.
 - b. Tractability...
 - c. Epistemological ambition...

TLO authors are often focused on expressivity, philosophical commitments, and generality of the approach, while application domain experts focus on "getting the things done". Expressivity (conceptual models) and computational efficiency (implementational models) are both important and necessary. We should find a good balance between them since there is still space to advance in the development of ontologies that value expressiveness.

Both tractability and expressivity are needed: a heterogeneous approach, where the same ontology can be provided at different levels of expressivity (e.g., from HOL to XML and RDBs) is advisable. There is a trade-off between expressivity and tractability, but it should be solved depending on the application case, with TLOs providing scalable expressivity versions to be chosen by the users. The same holds for reasoning, that may be useful in the AI field but generally not always used.

5. We need professional tools for Ontology Engineering. Tools that leverage on and that are aligned with TLOs. These include tools for validation (not only verification), code generators, complexity management tools, as well as tools that help with ontology reuse, including leveraging on ontology patterns and anti-patterns

Limited existing tools often impose constraints to the choice of ontology expressivity. However, the tractability needed by the applications may be reached by strengthening symbolic based reasoning, also to be proposed as an alternative to current AI approaches.

We should push for actions to raise the awareness about the need of tools for ontology development. Lack of good tooling and ecosystems that makes it easy and efficient to map existing data sources to ontological concepts is greatly slowing down the development.

6. There is a **lack of multi-disciplinary competences** within all the communities involved in ontology development and usage.

Potential users, scientific communities and industry are often affected by a competence bottleneck. There is a lack of people that can write good and reusable ontologies.

Clear communication, which problem classes can be solved with ontologies and even more, which problems can't be solved with ontologies. We need education and training, together with incentives for using ontologies in the scientific community and in industry.

7. Clear communication based on understanding of common principles, differences, and capabilities between TLOs communities, as well as concrete mappings, should be developed to prevent creating **ontological silos** that could jeopardize the overall TLOs efforts.

Tightening the TLO community providing a common discussion ground and the effort to understand similarities and differences can be the way to overcome this bottleneck. TLO communities should work together to strengthen their overall position towards policy makers. The OntoCommons initiative is an opportunity to achieve that.

8. MLO definition faces the challenges of **being coherent with the existing definitions or standards** provided by each discipline of interest (e.g., chemistry, metrology), and at the same time **to provide constraints on the formal structure of the ontological representation of the discipline** (e.g., taxonomy class levels). A clear separation between disciplines is not a realistic goal since each domain has already created its standard terminology and definitions.

We are always dealing with already established domain-specific classificatory systems that often lack rigorous and consistent logical structure and introduce ambiguities in the definitions. It is very important that a MLO at least reuses already established terms and standards, instead of starting from scratch from the top, using a pragmatic approach in which we propose changes also to already established standards, to improve their consistency in an ontological environment. It is reasonable to believe that abstractions can help bridging disciplines, even if some disciplines are very hard to be formally defined.

3.5.3 Implicit Feedback and Notes

The attendance through the three days' workshop showed no indication of preference for specific topics/methodological aspects of the OCES' outlined proposal.

The high attendance, and the proactivity of the engaged stakeholders reported in D2.1, was arguably a sign of there being a real interest in a (declaredly) pluralistic solution to the problem of the multiplicity of TLOs/MLOs. It also testified for the existence of a very large, aware, ontology community, focusing on different aspects of ontology development and usage – from philosophical matters to the practical usages.

Stakeholders appear willing to engage with ontologies, and aware of the role ontologies have in the path towards digitalization, especially to facilitate human-to-machine and machine-to-human interactions. Their core interest seems to be hinged on interoperability.

4. Workshop: "FATLOS"

Figure 5 - FATLOS banner

4.1 General Description of the Event

The **FATLOS** workshop was an **expert meeting** organized by WP2 and coordinated by CNR with the aim of answering the following points in the OntoCommons programme: "Identification of the alignment strategies and the practically achievable alignment level between TLOs, according to the conceptual correspondences identified in T2.2. Particular attention will be devoted to the possibility

of establishing a common Lightweight Top-Level Ontology, with a formal minimal characterization based on OntoClean meta-properties plus further minimal constraints".

The event was **subsequent to the alignment work in WP2 that led to the development of formal mappings between the DOLCE and BFO ontologies**, which was followed by an analogous alignment work between DOLCE and EMMO. These alignment activities are at the core of the **development of a Top Reference Ontology (TRO)** as the top stratum of an integrated OntoCommons ecosystem of application, domain, middle, and top level ontologies for data integration. Given this context, the ideal target of FATLOS was the **identification of a methodology suitable to develop coherent formal mappings across foundational ontologies**. Here coherency has two meanings as it applies globally at the level of the ecosystem and locally at the level of the individual ontology included in the system.

More practically, FATLOS gathered the foundational ontology community to:

- clarify the nature, formalization and limitations of formal mappings;
- clarify the suitable methodologies to develop these mappings;
- raise a general discussion on how to align ontologies;
- establish the state of the art on approaches and known problems;
- list problems that have not been clearly identified yet or are poorly understood;
- find the trade-off between logical/ontological precision and sustainable alignments
- provide priorities, guidelines, and principles that can guide research in this area

The workshop was divided into two parts. In the first part (lasting two hours) we had 8 speakers addressing the issues of FATLOS from their point of view and in the light of their experience in the field. The second part of the workshop (which extended to almost 3 hours), involving the collection of feedback (in any form), was organized as a discussion open to all the people attending the meeting. People were free to raise issues, present proposals, report on experiences, and comment based on their informed opinions, though the focus was individuated beforehand (see §4.4 infra).

4.2 Attendee Profile

As per the DoA, FATLOS specifically targeted **experts (on applied ontology and semantic web technologies)**. The participants were handpicked by members of the CNR based on their, and there was a high invitation to participation ratio (from whence the above average number of attendees for an expert meeting), as well as significant interest in delivering speeches. It was decided to have about a 1:2 ratio of OntoCommons-affiliated to OntoCommons-unaffiliated participants in order to favour the collection of external feedback without sacrificing the active involvement of members of the Consortium.

In what follows the full list of the participants can be found:

1. Alan Ruttenberg
2. Amaya Igartua
3. Ana Teresa Correia
4. Anne de Baas
5. Riccardo Baratella
6. Stefano Borgo
7. Chris Partridge
8. Claudio Masolo

- 9. Dragan Stokic
- 10. Emanuele Ghedini
- 11. Emilio Maria Sanfilippo
- 12. Emna Amdouni
- 13. Roberta Ferrario
- 14. Francesco Antonio Zaccarini
- 15. Frank Loebe
- 16. Hedi Karray
- 17. Heinrich Herre
- 18. J. Neil Otte
- 19. jbeverl4@jh.edu
- 20. Ludger Jansen
- 21. Matthew West
- 22. Michael Gruninger
- 23. Morais Fonseca Claudenir
- 24. Nicola Guarino
- 25. Paweł Garbacz
- 26. Raffaello Deturres
- 27. Arkopaul Sarkar
- 28. Torsten Hahmann

As for the attendees' Nationality, most of them were from Europe, the situation not being dissimilar from that presented in §3.2. The same considerations apply, *mutatis mutandis*, in this case as well.

4.3 Material Presented

Presentations were given by:

- Claudenir Fonseca (Free University of Bozen-Bolzano)
- Michael Gruninger (University of Toronto)
- Torsten Hahmann (University of Maine)
- Frank Loebe (University of Leipzig)
- Claudio Masolo (CNR)
- Chris Partridge (BORO Solutions)
- Arkopaul Sarkar (ENIT)
- Matthew West (Information Junction)

Specifically, Claudio Masolo and Arkopaul Sarkar presented material inherent to WP2's results and methodological proposals. The presentations were respectively first and last, to improve their salience for the discussion phase (and thus the collection of feedback).

Masolo gave an introduction to the work done to develop the **alignment of DOLCE and BFO** and presented the **strategy used to develop the formal mappings**. The presentation included the adopted strategy, the results, the problems discovered and possible ways to further extend the alignment. (The formal alignment, which is now part of the D2.4 deliverable, was distributed to the participants in advance.)

Sarkar discussed the **problem of aligning the top-level and the mid-level (MLO) ontologies** with a presentation entitled "Mid-level ontology(s) in OntoCommons - challenges". After the introduction of the OCES pluralistic approach and need for alignments, he addressed **the problem of identifying MLOs** and to separate concepts that should go into an TLO or an MLO (a topic that has not raised much attention yet). Sarkar listed 4 questions (reported below, as related to the feedback gathering activities) hoping that they could help to address relevant problems:

- **Q1:** What are the theoretical, technical, and methodological principles that MLO developer(s) may adopt to successfully apply the foundational theories of a TLO to model a set of generic concepts that can effectively serve multiple domain- and application-level views?
- **Q2:** Should there be a limit in the depth of coverage (thickness) constraining the number of levels of subtypes to a predefined number (e.g., no more than three levels of subtypes should be included for any given term or relation) as going down a hierarchy means the terms are increasingly specific and therefore less "mid-level"?
- **Q3:** What are the guidelines to invent (for technical need) generic concepts (often called 'bridge term') that are often positioned at the root or close to the root of an MLO to create a bridge between lower-level concepts (close to domain) and upper-level concepts from a TLO?
- **Q4:** What are the difficulties and concerns in developing a Middle Reference Ontology (MRO) that can integrate multiple MLOs and provide vertical alignment to different TLOs, and how to formulate a standard methodology or best practice guideline to alleviate such concerns?

Regarding the other presentations, **Loebe** reported the experience of the group that developed the GFO ontology. After a brief introduction of the ontology, he discussed of the problem of **understanding what it means that different logical expression share the "same content"** since we lack a notion of intentionally equivalent. This discussion was based on an attempt to align DOLCE and GFO that started in 2006 and that raised in the group some questions very much in line with the FATLOS topics like, e.g., how can one justify cross-ontology mappings and how should one prove their correctness. Then Loebe discussed the **distinction between theory interpretation** (with focus on consequence preserving translations), **interpretability** (with focus on "mutual" interpretability) **and the categorical approach called Institutions** (a framework that leads to cope with ontologies developed within distinct logic languages). Any alignment across ontologies leads quickly to inconsistencies which is hard to deal with without a strong notion of semantic equivalence for ontology. Towards the end Loebe suggested to complement these observations with Gruninger's work on ontology hierarchy and verification.

The presentation by **Gruninger** started right after and pointed to the **problem of isolating the ontological commitments of each ontology**. Then, he discussed three points:

- **verification:** characterization of the models of the ontology up to isomorphism, modularization of the ontology according to isomorphism, construction of modules of the ontology by amalgamation of those of the modules;
- **modularization:** modular decomposition gives insight to the commitments;
- **mapping** (translation definitions) across the ontologies that have the same ontological commitments He then discussed the modular amalgamation in PSL and in Dolce, and compared PSL and Dolce at this level of analysis. Gruninger added that he plans to apply the same approach on BFO.

Hahmann titled his presentation “Some Bits and Pieces on Mapping Ontologies” and started asking **what we actually want to map** and **what should a mapping preserve**: terms, concepts, inferences, individuals. In upper ontologies definitional extensions seems of limited use since most concepts are undefined/primitives, while structural equivalence is not enough because the same structure may be adopted with distinct meanings in different ontologies. Regarding automatic extraction of OWL axioms from FOL theories, Hahmann reported on his contribution at ISWC 2021 based on the **exploitation of matchings between formula structures**. This is an axiom level translation and there is no yet an evaluation of what happens to the inferences: to which extent are they preserved? In his contribution the evaluation was based on quality metrics. This is a pragmatic approach, perhaps not so good for TLOs, he concluded.

Matthew **West** started with the issues of “How Many Top Reference Ontologies?”. He reported the experience of the **National Digital Twin project in UK** updating the audience on goals and today's stage noting that the **core motivation is planning and disaster reaction, not sharing data**. This distinguishes their approach to that of OntoCommons. Towards the end West alerted about the **problem of facing the inconsistencies among TLOs**, something that at NDT aim to avoid using a unique TLO even though in the future they will have to find a way to include information coming from systems based on other ontological views. Since Chris **Partridge** was having connection problems, Matthew agreed to present the material of Partridge, which extended along similar lines as they are both involved in the NDT project (Partridge managed to join the workshop for the discussion session).

Finally, **Fonseca** presented the view of UFO but admitted that their group have not relevant experience in cross-ontology alignment problems as they tend to focus on their approach (there was a last-minute change in speaker from the UFO-group).

All the presentations made available by the speakers were collected.

4.4 Feedback Collection: Methodology

Given the profile of the attendees it was decided to collect feedback informally in a **specifically planned discussion phase**, rather than through the submission of a form. A survey would have failed to fully exploit the feedback-providers, due to the imposition of rigid constraints and pragmatic limitations inherent to the feedback-collection-tool; it was also deemed that, given the topics discussed and the aims of the workshop, the most innovative approaches and ideas, and the most actionable-upon feedback would have emerged through **dialectical exchange**.

Half the workshop's duration was dedicated to the discussion (and thus to the collection of feedback), and the reserved time was extended overtime due to the active engagement of the participants (a good number of the attendees stayed beyond the scheduled time). Active participants (in no particular order): West, Herre, Hahmann, Fonseca, Gruninger, Borgo, Masolo, Loebe, Ruttemberg, Garbacz.

In order to receive more targeted feedback, the focus was anticipated in the **call for contribution and participation** and made explicit via a list of problems which have a general relevance and a clear impact on the construction of mappings between foundational ontologies in FOL.

Explicit examples were given using BFO and DOLCE as in the following list:

- Notions and distinctions which are present only in one TLO and are "compatible" with the other TLO. For instance, (i) BFO has a `memberOf` relation which distinguishes objects from object aggregates; DOLCE could accommodate these kinds of entities under physical objects but it lacks the expressive power to characterize the object/aggregate distinction; vice versa (ii) DOLCE distinguishes agentive from non-agentive physical objects while BFO lacks an explicit reference to agentivity; (iii) BFO distinguishes spatial regions with different dimensionality (allowing the distinction between sites and continuant boundaries) while DOLCE just considers atomic vs. non atomic space regions (similarly for time); etc. In these cases, a definition of the more refined notions would require an extension of the original TLO. When are these extensions acceptable? Are these choices local to a TLO? Are there general guidelines?
- Notions and distinctions which are present only in one TLO and are "incompatible" with the other TLO. For instance, among qualities BFO considers relational qualities, i.e., qualities that depend on at least two different entities. DOLCE must be weakened to take into account this kind of entities (unless modelling these as individual qualities of the sum of the entities). Vice versa, DOLCE considers qualities of perdurants and qualities of qualities while BFO rules out them. Are there ways to reduce these incompatibilities remaining faithful to the meaning of each ontology? When are these applicable?
- Mappings requiring set-theoretical constructions. For instance, BFO considers spatiotemporal regions that, in terms of DOLCE, could be defined as sets of couples (space region, time interval). This construction would however require to move the mappings at the level of models or to extend the domain (and the signature) of DOLCE with spatiotemporal regions. When are these extensions acceptable? Are these choices local to a TLO? Are there general guidelines?
- Mappings which, from an ontological point of view, seem to make sense reveal different commitments of TLOs. For instance, the general notions of BFO-continuant and DOLCE-endurant seem to match. However, BFO does not allow material entities (that are not object aggregate) to be spatially co-localized while in DOLCE different material endurants can be spatially co-localized. There are then some axioms of BFO that cannot be proved starting from DOLCE and the mappings. Can these mappings be used? To what extent?
- Transfer of FOL mappings into OWL mappings It would be useful to find a systematic way to understand how the FOL-mappings can guide the establishment of the mappings between the OWL versions of the TLOs. If a number of FOL-mappings is available, how should they be used to guide the construction of OWL-mappings? What cases can arise? What if two TLOs use different strategies to generate the OWL-theory from their FOL-theories?

The presentations provided by members of the OntoCommons Consortium were tailored to the collection of feedback regarding the activities and methodological tools of WP2; explicit questions were posed as points of discussion throughout the presentations as a complement of the ones listed above.

The discussion itself was only **partially moderated** (when that was deemed necessary) by members of the Consortium as the goal was to let people discuss freely. Room for digressions was left in order to favour the emergence of valuable feedback and interesting approaches.

Notes were taken during the discussion-phase, which was also recorded (as all the workshop) for subsequent comparison and analysis.

4.5 Feedback Analysis

The reworked notes were used as a basis for the creation of a **list of the problems** in the FATLOS area at the centre of the **community concerns**:

- vocabulary vs axioms: there are many complete extensions possible for different modules. How should an ontology be specified beyond vocabulary?
- Should top classes in a TLO (e.g. GFO has 4) have their own local TLOs? After all, they cover very different areas with different primitives/relations.
- How to prove in ontology that a sentence is derivable from a theory?
- What is a standard/intended model?
- How to reach a balance between axiomatization and intended models?
- Concrete examples like in the recent Applied Ontology special issue on foundational ontologies give information that aides the alignment between TLOs.
- One should check if an ontology is coherent with the dataset one uses, and align the two for data quality, these dataset can provide information to map between ontologies.
- One dataset could be an intended model of the ontology and so be used to interpret the axioms (but how can data be trusted?)
- Discussion on how to use theorem provers to take advantage of the different features and peculiarities.
- Competency questions are not about getting answers but about checking if something makes sense and to test if the primitives/axioms cover all the concepts that might be relevant (e.g. asking the population of London in Celsius), but can this be done in practice with datasets?
- Do you need to clean the data before you can match to a TLO? Then which principles to you use to clean the data?
- Methodology for TLO alignment: which steps to follow and in which order? perhaps one can begin with an informal understanding of the other ontology and then start adding one axiom at a time (to ideally navigate the hierarchy while building a common core).
- What happens when the domains are different, e.g., time points and intervals have disjoint domains? perhaps one can translate all claims, but does this link/translation really make sense?
- Is it possible to start with small fragment of the ontologies? All concepts are strongly interlinked in foundational ontology so a concept/relation tends to be connected with most of (if not all) the ontology.
- When are two relations the same and when should they be seen as completely different relations? Examples are different formalizations of parthood, or the relationship between constitution and parthood.

It was also possible to individuate some common **points of agreement**, as per the list below:

- The way axioms are written can determine how modules are isolated: this is problematic.
- Theorem provers depend also on how one writes the primitives.
- Mappings across ontologies must be partial, this should not be surprising.
- TLO and dataset: Use the TLO to clean the data, use the data to validate the TLO (but there are doubts about what one can really achieve with this approach).

- Competency questions are not about getting answers but about checking if something makes sense and to test if the primitives/axioms cover all the concepts that might be relevant (e.g. asking the population of London in Celsius).
- Mapping specific/intended domains and mapping classes of models are different and point to distinct strategies.
- It still remains to be understood what we try to obtain with cross-ontology mappings.

4.5.1 *Holistic Analysis of the Explicit Feedback*

The explicit feedback was evaluated in the creation of the two lists above and object of discussion after the event had taken place and, again, prior to the creation of this report.

Two things appear evident in the analysis of the discussion and of the feedback received: (1) the discussion confirms some of the (non-technical) points emerged in Multi-Disciplinary Workshop, despite the specialisation of the community (see, for instance, the comments on the available practical tools); (2) at the moment even applied ontologies experts have **more open questions than answers**, both regarding the methodologies and theoretical points regarding the “standard” alignment of two ontologies, and even more so when it comes to the establishment of an interconnected OCEs.

This tendency substantially confirms the **frontrunner status of the OntoCommons Project**, yet **leaves open issues regarding the methodology and techniques employed**, as well as concerning the developed tools: while different groups have made use of different techniques given different ends (often less ambitious), it seems difficult to establish meters of comparison (or isolate comparable aspects), if not indicatively and only to a degree.

Even more difficult is to evaluate discussions on theoretically loaded technical points, as it is different to find a neutral ground due to the points specified above.

4.5.2 *Implicit Feedback and Notes*

The high invitation to participation ratio is significant of the **interest in the OntoCommons Project from the Applied Ontologies community**. Arguably, the **questions** raised in the FATLOS Workshop are **commonly deemed central by a significant majority**; it is fair to say that OntoCommons has established itself as a **leading actor** in research in the field on the back of the contributions of CNR and the **ambitious project**.

The fact that the discussion lasted more than the allocated time, and that a good number of participants stayed to the end of the Workshop, is also positive, and reinforces the point above.

The agreement reached on some technical points (specifically regarding automatic provers) was set to be taken into account for subsequent mappings among TLOs in the context of WP2. **The lack of definitive answers or shared consensus** regarding some of the questions posed in the expert meeting was properly taken into account and led to a further investment on a **pluralistic approach** (whereas possible) to **minimize the risks inherent in the exploration of uncharted territories**. Given the **lack of significant divergences with the respect to the Multidisciplinary Workshop**, it was deemed unnecessary to apply further corrective actions.

5. OntoCommons M18 – Consortium Meeting

Figure 6 - OntoCommons M18 – Consortium Meeting Banner

5.1 General Description of the Event

The **OntoCommons M18 Consortium Meeting** was a scheduled hybrid event organized in line with the projects' DoA. As such, more in-depth description of the event was deemed superfluous for this report. The events' agenda and all the relevant details are available to all the members of the Consortium.

The event was hosted by TUW, and took place in Wien the 4th and 5th of May (2022).

5.2 Attendee Profile

Members of the OntoCommons Consortium. Given the multidisciplinary nature of the project, the attendee profile is comparable to that of the Multidisciplinary workshop, if not slightly more oriented towards academia, with less representatives from the user side and industrial stakeholders.

Being the first Consortium Meeting not taking place fully online due to external factors, and the meeting preceding the M18 Technical Periodic Report, the event saw a large number of attendees. A full list of the participant (in person, and remotely) is available as part of the relevant OntoCommons' documentation.

5.3 Material Presented

All the presentations made at the event were collected by the organisers, and are currently available to the members of the Consortium as part of the material relative to the event. The presentation from WP2 is included.

The OntoCommons M18 – Consortium Meeting was the first formal instance in which the results of the cumulative efforts of T2.4 & T2.5 were exposed to the entirety of the OntoCommons Consortium. Specifically, **(a) the methodology for the alignment of TLOs** developed by T2.4 (and its first results with respect to the alignment of DOLCE and BFO), and **(b) the pluralistic approach to the alignment of MLOs** outlined by T2.5 were presented.

These elements occupy a core role in the creation of the OCES' framework and infrastructure; their shared understanding and acceptance in the Consortium, and their continuous improvement via feedback-loops has been deemed a precondition for the establishment of efficacious cooperation among the WPs, grounded roadmaps and dissemination activities conducive to the full exploitation of the provided tools, and, thus, to the achievement of the project's milestones.

In line with this premise, it was decided to reserve the majority of the time slot allocated to WP2 for their presentation and explanation, minimizing the time devoted to administrative aspects.

5.4 Feedback Collection: Methodology

It was decided to collect feedback informally during the meeting, gathering second-hand explicit feedback from demonstrators and other stakeholders through the presentations of other WPs, as the analysis of feedback received in different contexts of interactions, and filtrated by different parties, was deemed a resource worth keeping into account.

The conversations' natural flow in the days of the meeting led to exchanges regarding the relevant topics, so, in line with the expectations, there was generally no need to force the issue, with the risk of possibly vitiating the answers and compromising the feedback-gathering activities at large.

All the Consortium members were considered feedback-providers on equal grounds, and all the present members of WP2 involved in T2.4 & T2.5 and present on the spot (i.e., Emanuele Ghedini, Stefano Borgo, Arkopaul Sarkar, Francesco Antonio Zaccarini) contributed to the completion of the task.

The feedback was then aggregated and discussed informally in a WP meeting online, after the event had taken place, whereas the opinion of personnel attending remotely was also taken into account. Recordings of the event were also analysed by members of WP2 to ensure that all the feedback was gathered effectively, and to ensure the avoidance of biased impressions due to echo-chamber effects.⁶

⁶ The recordings were properly disposed of after use, in accordance with European Legislation.

5.5 Feedback Analysis

In this particular case, the distinction between explicit and implicit feedback is especially labile, and thus it was decided to analyse and report all the feedback across the board.

The comments made right after the WP2's contribution⁷ verted on the exploitability of the FOL alignments in the OWL framework, exploring practical aspects of the proposed methodology focus of the presentation. While there were almost no comments regarding the most technical aspects of the proposed methodology and the tools per se (in line with the expectations set at FATLOS), it was noticed that these points were often coming up in discussion.

The uptake was that the formal approach adopted by WP2 might have seemed too distant from the application level to be relevant, and that there were concerns regarding the exploitation of the results to be addressed. This was deemed reasonable and normal, as -at the time of the event- the results had yet to be fully transposed to the OWL framework, and there were no use-cases at hand. In any case, it was decided to be more forward on the benefits and limits of the approach, to clarify the role of the task in the context of the overall project and ensure that all the Consortium members had grounded and informed expectations, to maximise the efficacy of cooperative efforts.

There were also suggestions concerning the possibility of cooperating with other groups/projects working on standards for the representation of mappings, though further analysis revealed that the mappings operated at a lower level of complexity. However, in line with the suggestions, requirements to the end of the inclusion of additional information about who made Bridge-Concepts (and the relevant mappings) were considered for adoption to the end of improving FAIR-ness and transparency at every level, making domain experts' direct engagement more effective and trackable, and possibly increasing trust in the overall OCES framework and methodology.

Bridge-Concepts (and the overall methodology) generated some interest, though most of the participants seemed to endorse a wait-and-see stance, suspending judgement until application/exploitation, at least in test cases. While a rational and sensible stance, immediate feedback would have resulted more actionable upon, given the stage of development and divulgation, so it was decided to take the necessary steps to ensure the completion of the task in the context of the WP2 internal presentation (see § 6 infra).

When it comes to second-hand feedback from demonstrators and stakeholders, the discussions raised by WP1 and WP5's presentations were deemed particularly interesting. Beside confirming the general direction extrapolated from the analysis of the Multidisciplinary workshop's feedback, WP2 was reminded of the perceived importance of taxonomies and standardised vocabularies for stakeholders, as well as of their role as gateways to applied ontologies.

Since Bridge-Concepts were purposely created to meet said desiderata (among other things), the feedback was actioned upon by changing the relative weight of the advantages of said tools in their presentation to the general public. The importance of having strong connections with widely-employed standards was also stressed in the methodology concerning the engineering phase. It is difficult to evaluate the results of this trade-off in the short term, but there are reasons to assume that that led to an improvement in the perception of Bridge-Concepts (see §§ 6 to 8 infra).

⁷ Reported here anonymously, in accordance with GDPR.

6. Internal Presentation: WP2 Internal Presentation

Figure 7 - WP2 Internal Presentation Banner

6.1 General Description of the Event

The **WP2 Internal Presentation** was an event organized by WP2 specifically to the end of achieving a satisfactory level of **internal dissemination** of the methodology, crafted tools and overall results of the work package – possibly establishing and renewing cooperations among WPs, and to **gather feedback** to improve the latter via a feedback-loop mechanism.

More concretely, the aim was providing a formal presentation of the material contained in D2.4 and D2.5, and subsequent developments, focusing specifically on the OWL-framework and Bridge-Concepts – one of the alignment tools developed in the context of WP2 activities. This last choice has to be understood **in light of the feedback received at M18** (see §5.5.x).

The event took place on the 13/07/2022 in line with the DoA, and lasted around 3 hours, according to the plans (see figure 8 below for the full programme). Agenda and introductory material were distributed to the participants before the event. All the relevant documentation was provided to the attendees once the event had taken place.

15:00 WP2 Scope and Objectives (UNIBO)
15:10 TLOs: keys for interoperability (CNR)
15:40 MLOs: characterisation (ENIT)
15:55 Bridge concepts: unifying multi-perspective domain knowledge (ENIT, UNIBO, ATB):
 Introducing bridge concepts
 Bridge concept templates
 Overview of existing bridge concepts
16:30 Break
16:40 TRO/MRO OWL 2 DL Framework (UNIBO)
(GitHub repository, TRO/MRO module hierarchy, TRO/MRO in Protégé, Concepts in OWL DL)
17:00 Example of usage
17:30 Conclusions
17:45 Feedback
18:00 End

Figure 8 - Internal Presentation: Agenda

6.2 Attendee Profile

What has been said in §5.3 applies, *mutatis mutandis*, here. It was decided to invite Consortium members from all WPs, focusing on WP3 given the possibility of establishing a stronger cooperation relative to some of the tools developed by WP2 (i.e., Bridge-Concepts), resting on previous discussion in the context of WP3's T3.4' recurring meetings. The decision to include members belonging to all the WPs was finalised to reach an homogeneous permeation of tools and methodologies proposed in the Consortium, and to enable the gathering of feedback representing all the different facets and perspectives.

The invitation was extended to all the members of the Consortium. The participation and invitation to participation ratio were within expectations and met the conditions to ensure the satisfaction of the activity's goals (and the overall task).

6.3 Material Presented

As per the agenda above, the WP2 Internal Presentation was organised as a frontal presentation + (short) discussion, the latter being conducted during formal feedback-gathering activities. Speeches were delivered by Emanuele Ghedini, Claudio Masolo, Arkopaul Sarkar and Francesco Antonio Zaccarini, in no particular order; the presentation was supported by slides prepared beforehand and included a part dedicated to examples of usage and another covering the basics of Bridge-Concepts engineering, as a sort of training session (for WP3, which had expressed interest in co-opting the tool for the alignment of DLOs and lower level ontologies in the OCES).

In general, more time was reserved for the presentation of the TRO/MRO OWL framework (and its relationship with the FOL partial mappings provided by CNR in the context of T2.4) and Bridge-Concepts, both as a result of M18 feedback and to present new developments which were not yet included in the M18 Consortium Meeting presentation.

The presentations have been made available to all consortium members; recordings were made for internal usage (in-depth analysis of feedback, and -possibly- to be reused in training sessions).

6.4 Feedback Collection: Methodology

The methodology to collect feedback has been decided upon after the M18 Consortium Meeting, taking into account the results of the feedback-gathering activities concerning the latter. Ultimately, it was decided to (1) present the attendees with a **survey** after the presentation had taken place and (2) reserve some time for discussion, in order to also gather feedback informally in the form of knee-jerk reactions to the presented material.

Since gathering feedback regarding WP2's proposed methodology and tools was deemed of the utmost importance, especially at that stage of development (before making major commitments and proceeding with external dissemination of the approach), a number of measures were taken to facilitate feedback-providers and remove obstacles to the free expression of their opinion:

- Feedback-Providers were expressively informed that the data would only be employed anonymously and reported in aggregated fashion.
- It was explicitly stated that criticism was extremely welcome, and of the importance of making adjustments at that stage in the development cycle.
- Both general and detailed questions jointly prepared by WP2's members were provided to the attendees, to allow for different levels of engagement
- The feedback-providers were specifically informed that it was not expected of them to answer all the questions, and invited to answer only the questions they deemed more relevant or interesting.
- Time for the fill-in procedure was reserved from the event; the expected time for the completion of the task was estimated to be 10-15 minutes, assuming that answers were provided to most of the questions (though allegedly less).
- The link to the form was provided in case attendees preferred compiling the questionnaire after reflecting on/having assimilated the material.
- The means to set-up cooperations and long-term discussions was integrated in the form itself.
- WP2's members made themselves available to the feedback-providers in case some of the questions caused doubts.

As a result of the interactions which had taken place at M18, it was deemed important to ensure that the members of the Consortium felt at their ease in expressing doubt and possibly criticism. It appeared possible that considerations pertaining to the preservation of the status quo could negatively impact the feedback-gathering activity, and, thus, the entirety of the project.

Questions to track deviations in the community desiderata from the Multidisciplinary Workshop, and to improve the theoretical analysis of the landscape were also included in the questionnaire, though the ratio was kept in favour of the collection of more salient data. Given the pluralistic nature of the Consortium, some of the questions explicitly targeted specific classes of stakeholders, as their feedback -being stakeholders belonging to the targeted category and members of the Consortium- was deemed especially relevant. This was a further reason for the insurances on the treatment of the data outlined above, given the relatively contained number of attendees fitting within certain parameters.

6.4.1 Survey Specifics

The questionnaire presented to the feedback-providers included 23 effective questions. A reminder of the anonymity of the questionnaire, and how the data would be reported, was provided within the latter. An option to include personal information to set up longer exchanges and cooperation was integrated in the questionnaire.

Of the 23 macro-questions, 3 were rigidly constrained by a set of predefined options (of which, 2 required to express a degree of agreement with a statement in a graded range [1-7]); 20 were open questions with a high degree of freedom.

The choice of the grading system took into account the possibility of expressing a “neutral” evaluation, as a means of getting more relevant feedback, as well as recommendations in the choice of the scale coming from cognitive psychology.

The hypothetical time to fully compile the questionnaire was taken into account, despite the recommendation to answer only some of the questions and the assumed high degree of availability of the relevant feedback-providers (being members of the Consortium).

10/12/2022, 03:07

Feedback Survey (Copy)

Feedback Survey (Copy)

OntoCommons WP 2 Internal Presentation: 13/07/22

* Required

1. The data provided in this form will be employed by the OntoCommons Consortium to the end of improving ontology-alignment strategies and might be reported in an anonymous, aggregated form in public reports related to the OntoCommons project. *

I agree

2. The form can be filled anonymously, but feel free to add your contact info if you don't mind sharing them: we might contact you to discuss some of your suggestions and/or set up a cooperation

3. What is your general impression regarding the TRO/MRO framework architecture?

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10/12/2022, 03:07

Feedback Survey (Copy)

4. What do you think about the overall framework's usability? Do you have suggestions?

5. How important is **modularity**, and the ability to **customise and add modules**, when it comes to your willingness to engage with the framework?

Not Important Extremely Important

6. As a demonstrator or ontology user, do you think the TRO/MRO framework will make other **knowledge bases connected to the OCES more accessible to you?** (e.g. by making queries on bridge concepts to search for data)

7. What is your opinion on the introduction of **bridge-concepts** as way to facilitate the TLOs' exploitation for middle and domain experts?

10/12/2022, 03:07

Feedback Survey (Copy)

8. Do you feel like it is possible to elaborate one or more bridge-concepts to represent the **concepts related to your domain of expertise's standards** within the TRO/MRO framework?

9. Do you find the **bridge-concepts template** suitable to your needs? (e.g. does it help a reader to clearly identify concepts)

10. How do you feel about bridge-concepts template **domain resources section**, whose target is the **non-ontology educated reader**? Do you have any suggestions on how to improve it?

11. How do you feel about bridge-concepts template **alignment section**, whose target is the **ontology educated reader**? Do you have any suggestions on how to improve it?

10/12/2022, 03:07

Feedback Survey (Copy)

12. Do the **bridge-concept elucidation** and **alignment comments** help you understand the rationale underlying the choices made, distilling the domain resources into ontology usable concepts?

13. What **difficulties do you expect** integrating your MLO/DLO into the TRO/MRO framework?

14. You had the chance to check a few bridge-concepts elucidations: are they too dispersive or too brief?

15. How much does the required time to consult a resource impact your willingness to engage with it?

I don't take it into account It is extremely important

16. What are your **expected benefits** (specific to your case) from the alignment of your existing or new DLO to an **existing TLO/MLO**?

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10/12/2022, 03:07

Feedback Survey (Copy)

17. How would you benefit from aligning your existing or new DLO to **other existing DLOs**?

18. Is your DLO a **simple taxonomy**? If not, what kind of **relations** are important to you?

19. How do you think **cross-domain alignments** would impact you as a stakeholder? (e.g. data analysis, annotating unstructured text, querying data from multiple federated queries)

20. Which **conceptual/methodological tools** would facilitate the manual mapping process (MLO-TLO, DLO-MLO), if any? (e.g., the use of Ontology Design Patterns, a tutorial exemplifying typical cases)

10/12/2022, 03:07

Feedback Survey (Copy)

21. According to your personal experience, could you identify some **unique characteristics of an MLO** to distinguish it from some TLO and DLO?

22. Which are the ontologies that you already use (or have some knowledge of) **which you consider MLOs?** (especially for what concerns the materials and manufacturing domain)

23. Could you mention a topic to be **ideally covered by an MLO?** (please mention an existing MLO for this topic if available)

24. What is the **alignment level that the TRO/MRO framework should provide** and that you consider to be the minimal requirement for your use-case scenario?

- standardised vocabulary (i.e. agreement on concepts and labels)
- taxonomical alignment (i.e. class hierarchy)
- ontological alignment (i.e. taxonomy and relations)
- o ontological alignment complete with tools for reasoning

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10/12/2022, 03:07

Feedback Survey (Copy)

25. Please provide a brief comment on your answer above.

6.5 Feedback Analysis

6.5.1 Holistic Analysis of the Explicit Feedback

Given the results of the survey, both the OWL framework and Bridge-Concepts were **well-received** overall, though (1) the **wait-and-see attitude** from M18 was substantially confirmed (which resulted in limited amounts of actionable-upon feedback) and (2) the members of the Consortium appeared (comparatively) **less positive on the possibility of engaging actively in the development of the framework and the tools**, at least in the short term.

In particular, Bridge-Concept engineering was **perceived as a complex activity** requiring the involvement of ontologists beside domain experts – contra one of the aims for their creation, an issue which had to be solved to ensure **scalability**, especially since the latter were (nonetheless) taken-up by WP3 as the designed tool for the alignment of lower level ontologies as a result of the event. The shift in presentation towards aspects related to the possibility of establishing a vocabulary for formal ontologies connected to golden standards (as a result of the feedback-loop) appeared to have the desired effect, but **possibly cast into the background some technical aspects** related to Bridge-Concepts' formal role in the OntoCommons EcoSystem.

The OWL Framework was deemed adequate and satisfactory, both from a theoretical and, especially, from practical point of view. The possibility of selecting sub-architectures of the OCES depending on the needs of the users, via **modularisation**, was deemed extremely useful from a practical point of view, and it was suggested to advertise the result to the relevant demonstrators and stakeholders.

Both of the above points were generally confirmed as tendencies in the open discussion following the presentation, and plans were made for the cooperation between WP2 and WP3, and dissemination.

However, the explicit feedback reconfirmed the necessity of investing resources in the improvement and specification of the methodology, (internal) dissemination efforts, and in the application of the tentative methodological resources and tools to practical cases for **testing**.

In line with the expectations (based on the results of FATLOS and M18), not much feedback was gathered with respect to the more technical or stakeholder-specific questions in the survey, nor were they touched upon in the course of the open discussion.

As for what concerns the comparison with the results of the first Multidisciplinary workshop, once again **no major deviations in desiderata and perception of the general landscape were individuated**, thus no changes in the project trajectory were deemed necessary.

6.5.2 *Implicit Feedback and Notes*

The choice of leaving the selection of the questions to be answered to the feedback-providers did not give the expected results and it was not possible to obtain meaningful data from the analysis of the questions preferred by the feedback-providers. Overall, it is also not clear whether the assurances regarding the treatment of the data and WP2's stance on criticism had the desired effects.

In the answers and open discussion, a general lack of discrimination between the use of "term" and "concept" was noticed. This was deemed a possible source of misunderstanding down the line, endangering the understanding of the proposed methodology and of the theoretical assumptions. Promoting a multidisciplinary approach to the resolution of problems is one of the staples of OntoCommons, so it seems appropriate that the issue should be tackled by means of clarification rather than lossy simplification.

Doubts were also detected on the notion of Elucidation, assimilated to that (commonsensical) of Definition, or understood given its use in BFO.

That aside, the use of the jargon introduced in the presentation was appropriate, and sign of the permeation of the expounded material.

The willingness of WP3 to adopt the proposed methodology for the alignment of lower level ontologies in the OCES was considered a sign of the positive reception of WP2's results.

7. Workshop: "FOMI22"

Figure 9 - FOMI22 Banner

7.1 General Description of the Event

FOMI (Formal Ontologies Meet Industries) is an “international forum where academic researchers and industrial practitioners meet to analyse and discuss application issues related to methods, theories, tools and applications based on formal ontologies”.⁸

The event recurs annually; the 2022 edition was hosted by ENIT, with the workshop taking place in Tarbes (France) from the 12th to the 15th of December (thus, lasting 4 days). The workshop features a number of sessions organised by OntoCommons and some of the Consortium’s partners.

The primary goal of this event was to provide a chance for academia and industry to gather, presenting and discussing application issues and desiderata related to methods, theories, tools, and applications based on formal ontologies in the domains of manufacturing, materials, and, derivatively, domains taking part in shared value chains.

According to the event pamphlet (<https://ontocommons.eu/news-events/events/12th-international-workshop-formal-ontologies-meet-industry-fomi22>) the explicit aims of the 2022 edition of FOMI were “to collect and share useful experiences and lessons learned by the presentations from both academia and industry:

- New research results;
- New insights on known problematic issues;
- Experience with problems in ontology application;
- Successes and observations in ontology implementation;
- Lessons learned on the best way to apply ontological methodologies and tools to real-world situations;
- Demo of ontology-based applications in industry”.

A full list of the topics was made available to the attendees, and is reported in what follows:

⁸ See <https://iaoa.org/index.php/about/events/> for some information about the history of FOMI, and a more detailed introduction.

Problems in ontology application:

- Practical issues in using ontologies in enterprises;
- Real cases of successful/unsuccessful use of ontology;
- From legacy systems to ontology-driven systems;
- Application of FAIR principles for ontologies in the industry;
- Experiences acquired wrt ontology-based software applications (e.g., tools for developing ontologies).

Ontology and knowledge management:

- Ontological methodologies in data modelling and knowledge management;
- Adaptation of formal ontologies for companies and organizations;
- Ontology development and change within companies/organizations;
- Ontology effectiveness and evaluation;
- Ontologies for the know-how;
- Ontologies for corporate knowledge.

Ontology in practice:

- Ontologies for engineering (manufacturing, design, etc.);
- Ontologies for material science;
- Ontologies for electronic catalogues, e-commerce, e-government, etc.;
- Ontologies for marketing;
- Ontologies for finance;
- Ontologies for medical sciences;
- Ontologies for IoT.

A complete agenda of the event is reported infra for the sake of completeness. The relevant sessions have been marked for ease of readability, and will be presented and discussed in §7.3.

Time		Sessions - Grand Amphitheater
08:45	09:30	Introduction to FOMI 2022 - Hedi Karray, Emilio Sanfilippo
09:30	10:15	Keynote speech - Stephan Grimm
10:15	10:45	Functional modelling in engineering: A first comparison of approaches on two problems - Francesco Compagno
10:45	11:15	Taxonomy of Manufacturing Joining Operations based on Process Characterization - Arkopaul Sarkar
11:15	11:30	Coffee break
11:30	12:00	Ontology for Industrial Engineering: A DOLCE compliant approach - Walter Terkaj
12:00	12:30	The Industrial Ontology Foundry (IOF) - Milos Drobnakovic
12:30	13:00	The CHAMEO ontology: Exploiting EMMO's multiperspective versatility for capturing materials characterisation - Pierluigi Del Nostro
13:15	14:40	Lunch Break
14:45	15:30	Keynote speech - Markus Stumptner
15:30	16:00	Towards an ontology of offshore petroleum production equipment - Mara Abel
16:00	16:30	Requirements for an Ontology of Asset Management - Megan Katsumi
16:30	16:45	Coffee break
16:45	17:05	Multi-perspective approach to integrate domain-specific semantics into the system model - Elaheh Maleki
17:05	17:25	KIDE4Assistant: an Ontology-Driven Dialogue System Adaptation for Assistance in Maintenance Procedure - Cristina Aceta, Patricia Casla, Izaskun Fernandez,
End of Day 1		

<h1>Formal Ontologies meet Industry</h1> <p>Second day (13th): OntoCommons</p>			
Time	Sessions		
08:30 - 09:15	Introduction to OntoCommons and roadmap - Hedi Karray [Grand Amphitheater]		
09:15 - 10:00	Keynote speech 1 - Heiner Oberkamp [Grand Amphitheater]		
10:00 - 10:15	Coffee break		
Parallel sessions	Room E1	Room E2	Room E3
Session title	Upper Ontology and Standards for Industry - Host: Emilio Sanfilippo	Upper Ontology and Standards for Materials Science - Host: Thomas Anke	FAIR Domain Ontologies for Industry - Host: Yann Le Franc
10:15 - 10:45	Presentation 1 - Stefano Borgo	Presentation 1 - Gerhard Goldbeck	Introduction and How to make Ontologies FAIR - Yann Le Franc
10:45 - 11:15	Presentation 2 - David Leal	Presentation 2 - Emanuele Ghedini	A concrete step toward FAIR ontologies : publishing ontologies in specialised ontology repositories - Arkopaul Sarkar Manual evaluation: using the FAIR Semantics recommendations - Yann Le Franc
11:15 - 12:00	Panel Discussion: Ontology-based standardisation of industrial data - Host: Hedi Karray. Panellists: Serm Kulvatunyou, Elisa Kendall, David Leal, Michela Magas	Panel discussion: Ontology and standards for material science - Host: Joana Morgado. Panellists: Gerhard Goldbeck, Emanuele Ghedini, Silvana Muscella, Norman Swindells, Alexandru Todor.	Automated evaluation: FOOPS ! - Maria Poveda OFAIRe and OntoPortal - Clement Jonquet Toward the harmonisation of ontology metadata - Yann Le Franc
12:00 - 13:30	Lunch break		
Parallel sessions	Room E1	Room E2	Room E3
Session title	Domain ontology harmonisation for Industry - Host: Lan Yan and Mirco Soderl	Domain ontology harmonisation for materials science - Host: Gerhard Goldbeck	Industrial demonstration
13:30 - 14:00	Presentation 1 - Emilio Sanfilippo and Arkopaul Sarkar	Presentation 1 - Joana Morgado, Dirk Helm	Cirqolor - Roy Brooks
14:00 - 14:30	Presentation 2 - Barry Smith Presentation 3 - Noel Vizcaino	Materials Informatics for Advanced Materials - Pedro Portella	SimPhoNy: knowledge-graph based interoperability - José Manuel Dominguez
14:30 - 15:15	Panel Discussion: Domain ontology harmonisation for industry - Host: Izaskun Fernandez. Panellists: Chris Partridge, Emilio Sanfilippo, Alejandro Salado, Will Sobel	Panel Discussion: Domain ontology harmonisation for materials science - Host: Gerhard Goldbeck. Panellists: Heiner Oberkamp, Dirk Helm, Thomas Hanke, Alexandru Todor	Airbus - Rebecca Arista
15:15 - 15:30	Coffee break		
15:30 - 16:15	Keynote speech 2 - Elisa Kendall [Grand Amphitheater]		
16:15 - 17:00	Keynote speech 3 - Chris Partridge [Grand Amphitheater]		
17:00 - 17:15	Vote of thanks		
Onward: social events			

Formal Ontologies meet Industry

Third day (14th): Industrial Ontology Foundry and Domains

Time		Sessions			
09:00	09:15	Welcome Note and Introduction - Dimitris Kiritsis [Grand Amphitheater]			
09:15	10:00	Keynote speech 1 - Serm Kulvatunyou [Grand Amphitheater]			
10:00	10:30	Coffee break			
Parallel sessions		Room E1	Parallel sessions	Room E2	Room E3
		Production and Supply-chain - PT.1 Hosts: Dušan Šormaz and Farhad Ameri		Products, Systems and Digital Twins PT.1 - Hosts: Ana Correia and Jinzhi Lu	Materials, Quality and Maintenance PT.1 - Hosts: Folvos Psarommatis, Thomas Hanje, Melinda Hodgekiewicz
10:30	10:50	Overview of progress in IOF PPS ontologies - Dušan Šormaz	10:30 10:45	IOF Systems Engineering - Jinzhi Lu	IOF Maintenance Reference ontology - Melinda Hodgekiewicz
10:50	11:10	Current State of Supply Chain Reference Ontology - Farhad Ameri	10:45 11:00	Towards an Ontology of the Problem Domain - Alejandro Salado	Data cleaning – a practical and value-adding use case for modular ontologies - Melinda Hodgekiewicz
11:10	11:40	Enhance metamodels approach supporting models for manufacturing (MfM) methodology - Fernando Mas	11:00 11:15	Ontologies' role in a digital twin development - Chris Partridge	Are ontologies a practical solution to digitalising maintenance? - Pavan Addepalli
11:40	12:00	Supporting Product Services Systems over the Operational Life - Oliver Stoll, Shaun West	11:15 11:30	Ontology, Modelling and System - Ming Yu	Ontology-Based Maintenance: The Use Case of BLMGroup in Ontocommons - Francesco Compagno
12:00	12:30	Panel discussion: Production planning and scheduling - Host: Farhad Ameri Panelists: Will Sobel, Sebastian Scholze, Oliver Stoll, Shaun West	11:30 11:45	Converging ontology and MBSE to support aircraft manufacturing system design - Rebeca Arista and Xiaochen Zheng	The role of ontologies in Industrial environments and challenges - Alessia Focareta
			11:45 12:25	Panel discussion: Systems Engineering - Host: Jinzhi Lu. Panellists: Rebeca Arista, Xiaochen Zheng, Ming Yu, Alejandro Salado	Panel discussion: Maintenance - Host: Pavan Addepalli. Panellists: Melinda Hodgekiewicz, Hedi Karray, Stefano Borgo, Emilio Sanfilippo, Yves Keraron

12:30		14:00		Lunch break				
Parallel sessions		Room E1	Parallel sessions		Room E2	Parallel sessions		Room E3
		Production and Supply-chain - PT.2 Hosts: Dušan Šormaz and Farhad Ameri			Products, Systems and Digital Twins - PT.2 Hosts: Ana Correia and Jinzhi Lu			Materials, Quality and Maintenance -PT.2 Hosts: Foivos Psarommatis, Thomas Hanke, Melinda Hodgekiewicz
14:00	14:20	An ontological approach for Traceability in Agri-food Supply Chains - Farhad Ameri	14:00	14:15	PSS Ontology – current status and outlook - Ana Correia	14:00	14:15	IOF Materials Science and Engineering Workgroup - Thomas Hanke
14:20	14:40	An Ontology-based Engineering system to support aircraft assembly process design - Xiaochen Zheng and Rebeca Arista	14:15	14:30	Product Service Systems in Industry - Giuditta Pezzotta and Fabiana Pirola	14:15	14:30	Matportal.org The Repository for Materials Science and Engineering Ontologies - Alexandru Todor
14:40	15:00	Presentation 3 - Alejandro Salado	14:30	14:45	Digital twin innovation potential for the materials and manufacturing industries - Dan Isaacs	14:30	14:45	IOF/Mat-o-Lab Toolchain - Thomas Hanke
15:00	15:45	Panel discussion: Capability - Host: Arkopaul Sarkar Panelists: Barry Smith, Stefano Borgo, Farhad Ameri, Will Sobel	14:45	15:00	Digital twin innovation potential for the materials and manufacturing industries - Michel Sauvage	14:45	15:25	Panel discussion: Materials Science - Host: Gerhard Goldbeck. Panelists: Alexandru Todor, Thomas Hanke, Heiner Oberkamf.
			15:00	15:15	Products and Services bridge concepts - Francesco Antonio Zaccarini	15:25	15:45	Zero Defect Manufacturing the next standard for quality assurance - João Pedro Mendonça uninova
			15:15	15:45	Panel discussion: Products and Services - Host: Ana Correia. Panelists: Dragan Stokic, Xiaochen Zheng, Sebastian Scholze, Marcela Vegetti or Gabriela Henning			
15:45		16:00		Coffee break				
16:00	16:25	What can ontological analyses of value and risk teach us about goals, plans, and prevention? - Jim Logan	16:00	16:15	Standards-Based Self Aware Manufacturing Systems - William Sobel	16:00	16:15	The role of terminology standardization in the quality assurance domain - Yusuf Yilmaz
16:25	16:50	Panel Discussion: Production Planning and Scheduling - Host: Dusan Sormaz Panelists: Fernando Mas, Jim Logan, Mara Abel	16:15	16:30	Digital twins and the problem of model-induced escape - Barry Smith	16:15	16:30	The role of semantics in Industrial IoT (IIoT) towards Zero Defect Manufacturing - John Soldatos
			16:30	16:45	Impact of digital twin innovation in the industrial sector - Sjoerd Rongen	16:15	16:30	Systems modelling with Information Modelling Framework (IMF) and the impact to the manufacturing industry - Arild Waaler
17:00	17:45	Keynote speech - Mara Abel [Grand Amphitheater]						
17:45	18:15	IOF Governance and Architecture - Will Sobel [Grand Amphitheater]						
End of Day 3								

Time		Sessions								
08:45	09:00	Welcome and Summary - Hedi Karray [Amphitheater B]								
FOMI posters presentations [Amphitheater B]										
09:00	09:15	Towards An Open Translation Environment for Supporting Translators in The Material Domain. - Florina Piroi								
09:15	09:30	Bring together model and business ontologies for protective coatings. - Salim Belouettar								
09:30	09:45	Use of ontologies to structure and manage digital technical data of industrial assets: First steps towards an ecology of knowledge in multi-energies industry. - Jean-Charles Leclerc								
09:45	10:00	An implementation of OWL-S to Support Semantic Discovery for SWIM. - Luis Antonio Rodriguez								
10:00	10:30	Industrial presentation (Perpetual Lab) - Gianmaria Bullegas								
10:30	11:00	Industrial Presentation (Total Energies) - Jean-Charles Leclerc								
11:00	11:15	Coffee break								
Parallel sessions		<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 50%;"></th> <th style="width: 50%;"></th> </tr> <tr> <th style="text-align: center;">Room E1</th> <th style="text-align: center;">Room E2</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Training session 1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Training session 2</td> </tr> <tr> <td> 11:30 13:00 How to develop ontology following OCES methodology - Host: Emanuele Ghedini, Francesco Zaccarini, Arkopaul Sarkar </td> <td> FAIR Implementation Profiles - Barbara Magagna </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Room E1	Room E2	Training session 1	Training session 2	11:30 13:00 How to develop ontology following OCES methodology - Host: Emanuele Ghedini, Francesco Zaccarini, Arkopaul Sarkar	FAIR Implementation Profiles - Barbara Magagna
Room E1	Room E2									
Training session 1	Training session 2									
11:30 13:00 How to develop ontology following OCES methodology - Host: Emanuele Ghedini, Francesco Zaccarini, Arkopaul Sarkar	FAIR Implementation Profiles - Barbara Magagna									
13:00	14:00	Lunch								
Onward: social events										

7.2 Attendee Profile

As per the event mission, the Workshop was targeted at academics and industrial practitioners. Compared to the other events considered up until this point, the balance was shifted towards the **application level**, with a high participation of **end-users stakeholders**, and **possible investors**.

Despite the collaboration with the OntoCommons' Consortium, many of the invitees were outsiders (not demonstrators nor industrial partners), and, thus, the event provided a great chance for external **dissemination** (to the general public), networking, and **comparison with the strategies developed and employed by different groups**, at different levels and with different goals in mind.

The FOMI Workshop attempted to reach a more **diverse "International" community**, but (even being a hybrid event) there appeared to be a higher participation from European Countries due to contingent matters (location, travel regulation, timetable etc.). As in previous cases, this should not have affected the feedback-gathering activities (nor the comparison with other approaches) in any meaningful way. More details about the participants will be provided in a further report in the context of WP3's activities.

7.3 Material Presented

Material resulting from the efforts of T2.4 & T2.5 was presented by Emanuele Ghedini, Arkopaul Sarkar, Gherard Goldbeck, Francesco Antonio Zaccarini. All the presentations were collected and recorded, and were made available online to the general public by the organisers. Rapporteurs were appointed for some of the session, and their reports collected.

In general, both **practical and methodological developments were presented**, with a focus on topics and aspects whose salience (and advertising potential) had been **identified through the analysis of feedback from previous events**. **The attendee profile was kept in due account**. Detailed summaries of the talks will be provided only in the upcoming section, through rapporteurs' reports when available, to avoid redundancies.

More details on the talks, and the event in general, will be made available within the context of WP3 reporting activities.

7.4 Feedback Collection: Methodology

It was decided to make use of the **rapporteur notes**, when available, to gather objective, semi-formal feedback in an unintrusive fashion, in cooperation with the event organisers (ENIT); the collection of feedback proceeded via analysis of the **recordings** (conducted by members of WP2) whenever the rapporteur notes were not available. **Informal feedback** was also gathered throughout the event by all the Consortium members attending FOMI22 in person, and the members of WP2 specifically.

In what follows, the summaries relative to the relevant sessions are provided (by means of rapporteur notes when possible).

Upper Ontology and standards for Material Science: Presentations 1 & 2 | Gherard Goldbeck & Emanuele Ghedini (respectively)

Session 2-1-3B

Rapporteur Template

Upper Ontology and Standards for Material Science

Chair

Joana Morgado (Fraunhofer IWM, Germany)

Rapporteur

Francesco Antonio Zaccarini (Unibo, Italy)

Session presenter at Podium Discussion

Joana Morgado (Fraunhofer IWM, Germany)

Introduction

This session looks into the needs and desiderata for upper level ontologies, and Top Level Ontologies specifically, with respect to Material Sciences.

Objectives

- Defining the requirements for Upper level ontologies for Material Sciences.
- Defining further domain-specific needs and desiderata.
- Investigate how ontologies -and ontologies' interoperability- can be improved taking inspiration from Material Sciences' methodological principles and procedural staples.
- Providing an example of an ontology tailored to the needs and desiderata of Material Sciences: EMMO (Elementary Multiperspective material Ontology).

Impulse Notes, Questions, Remarks

Presentation 1

Gerhard Goldbeck (Goldbeck Consulting Limited, UK)

Title Upper ontology and Standards for Material Science

Abstract: Underlying the plurality of scientific disciplines falling under the label of Material Sciences there are shared methodological principles and assumptions; there are good reasons to think that they might as a compass for defining domain-specific requirements for upper level ontologies, going ways towards the establishment of a scientifically-grounded basis for interoperability.

<https://www.ontocommons.eu/>

 company/ontocommons

- How do you deal with different locations of Space and Time?
 - EMMO's approach will be presented in the next talk. There is no way around if not leaving different options open to enable lower level ontologies.
- How do you deal with different, incompatible standards/definitions?
 - Via pluralism: different perspectives are relevant in different contexts.
- From an applicative point of view, as supplier, at the end of the day I have a product, asset: I need to control or understand where failure can actually occur, and prevent them. Have you looked at integrating the process-level information? Are you looking at the practicality of what might be required in the future?
 - You have to have a system in place to properly describe what's happening; to give meaning to data. This should be the key to addressing the problems at the applicative level. In practice, it might not be an easy thing to do, or to find the right framework.

Presentation 2

Emanuele Ghedini (Unibo, Italy)

Title Addressing Materials Science Upper level Ontological Needs with the EMMO

Abstract: EMMO, the Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology, is an Upper Level Ontology developed in the context of a number of projects with governance by the European Materials Modelling Council. It has been developed by practitioners of Material Sciences, with the explicit aim of producing a framework consistent with scientific principles and methodologies.

Take-aways:

- EMMO provides strong foundations for the multiscale representation of materials, allowing the users to operate at different levels of detail.
- EMMO attempts to provide a way to describe the world by means of employing the categories of applied sciences, being respective of their methodologies and assumptions; one of the three primitive relations the ontology is founded upon, causality, is both consistent with Feynman's diagrams, and capable of providing a basis for a Special Relativity-friendly representation of spacetime.
- EMMO avoids ambiguities arising in categorisation by imposing accuracy via in-built constraints.

Take-aways:

- Material Sciences' shared methodological principles and assumptions can act as a compass in defining requirements and desiderata for both the specifics and overall design of Upper level Ontologies.
- Industry requires faster development and innovation cycles, which are hinged on digitalisation and collaboration. There is thus a need of a unique way of representing materials, processing and the according devices.
- Meaningful interoperability and ontology usage further requires rich, precise (shared) materials knowledge, which can only be achieved by understanding the core methods and principles of the relevant sciences (and grounded on the latter).
- It is pivotal to remember that ontologies have a descriptive nature, leaving data processing and mathematics to separate implementations.
- The ability to properly connect physical entities and models is a core requirement for Upper Level Ontologies when it comes to Material Sciences. Specific attention should be dedicated to matters related to observation, measurement and metrology.
- Upper level Ontologies should allow for a multiscale representation of matter, and provide clear foundations for Lower level Ontologies.
- Upper level Ontologies should allow for a multiscale representation of the characteristics of materials, allowing for elements of pluralism.
- There is a need for Upper Level Ontologies' concepts/ontological entities to establish relations to Standards, even in case they are mutually incompatible, qua representative of goals and desiderata from different disciplines. A pluralistic approach, representing concepts in the most "natural" way possible, is recommended.

Q&A:

- In ChEBI there is a description of Atom: is it in agreement with what you are suggesting?
 - We are currently attempting to evaluate where the concepts employed by different ontologies stand, with respect to reference points; we have noticed that there are details missing in the formal and informal characterisation of Atom in ChEBI; then again, it's important to keep in mind that ChEBI was made with a certain purpose in mind.
- How do you deal with use-oriented classifications, like the ontological representation of materials' "performance"?
 - The real question is whether "performance", however it is understood from an applicative point of view, can be connected with the deeper experimental behaviour of materials. If not, the connection can only be with expectations and observations, so the ontological framework should address it that way.

- EMMO's multiperspective approach allows users and stakeholders to focus on the points they are most interested in (hiding complexity in the process). A combined use of multiple perspectives allows for a more flexible and in-depth representation of the world.
- EMMO's separation of semantics and syntax, conjointly with semiosis, arguably properly captures the principles underlying observation and measurement in material Sciences.

Q&A:

- Regarding the semiotic perspective: what happens in semiotic processes involving assumptions, like if someone infers the existence of a cat from the observation of a cat's tail.
 - In the described example the tail is an index for the cat. The entity "tail" falls under index, and you can declare that this individual is an index for a certain kind of entities. EMMO is thus capable of representing this semiotic process.

Other Related information and documents

- <https://emmc.eu/>
- <https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMO>

Discussion points and questions (For Panels)

- There needs to be some way to connect the engineering level to the fundamental level, and of appropriate standards.
- Are philosophically grounded partitions of the logical space apt to act as foundations for TLOs in this context?
 - They can be – as long as the needs of Material Sciences are respected.
- Should there be a system of ontologies? Levels of Ontologies? The multiplicity of standards, like the multiplicity of ontologies creates difficulties in interoperability. Are references among different standards enough? They are employed to good effect in the context of ISO Standards, so that might represent a good starting point.
- TLOs are a mechanism to communicate and reach stakeholders; they might facilitate the natural selection of standards, and the emergence of preconditions for interoperability.
- Most existing ontologies are not a standard: should they be made into standards? It is unclear whether the standardization of ontologies would go ways towards improving interoperability, and not create an intractable problem given issues related to scalability. As a maxim, *common understanding* should prevail over the

creation of new standards. Standardization should rather be a way to improve common understanding and arrive at a consensus.

- It might be useful to distinguish between de facto standards, and nominal standards, and focus on creating connections among the ones which survived “natural selection”.
- Demonstrators can act as the determining factor, as they are the agents of natural selection. Adoption is key.
- A structured approach to the definition of terms connected to standards should prove fruitful in practice. Ontological levels can be a basis for this work.
- Should ontologies’ development’s workflow be changed to improve interoperability?
 - Some formatting and syntactic requirements would definitely go ways towards improving interoperability, and they are being defined in the context of OntoCommons.

Product and Services: Bridge-Concepts | Francesco Antonio Zaccarini

In his presentation, Francesco Antonio Zaccarini provided a general introduction to Bridge-Concepts and a specific case of application in the context of WP3 activities, and -specifically- in the Product and Service Focus Group.

The presentation touched on the background assumptions and the exposition of the theoretical framework, showing the benefits of the tool within, and without, the OCES (a more detailed exposition was produced in the training session; this presentation also served to advertise for the latter). Particular attention was dedicated to contextualizing the tool with respect to the relevant issues it purports to solve, and to provide a concrete application case, capable of grounding the methodology for stakeholders and possible investors.

Q&A: Most of the questions focused on the tool presented (Bridge-Concepts).

An attendee asked whether the creation of a plurality of Bridge-Concepts for a given domain would result in a new ontology. It was specified that Bridge-Concepts are stand-alone, unless specific goals have to be met, and thus they can support the creation of new ontologies (already connected to the OCES) but cannot become -per se- a new ontology (as that would compromise modularity and increase the system’s fragility).

It was also asked whether Bridge-Concepts can be considered mappings, and it was answered that they are mediators of a multiplicity of mappings, given the OCES’ aims and the hub-and-spoke structure.

Worries were put forward on whether Bridge-Concepts would be considered “just another concept” in the arena, though they might lead to an overall improvement at the level of documentation – facilitating connections and thus interoperability, and clarifications requested on the notion of “ontology neutrality”.

How to develop ontologies following the OCES methodology | Emanuele Ghedini, Arkopaul Sarkar & Francesco Antonio Zaccarini

The training session can be considered the first real in-depth exposition of T2.4 & T2.5's results targeted to industrial practitioners and stakeholders.

The material from the Internal Presentation was reworked keeping in due consideration the diverse target audience, and the feedback received. More time was dedicated to the presentation of the OWL framework, and to use-oriented tools developed within the Consortium. The general aim was showing how the different tools could together provide industrial stakeholders with a coherent package, tailored to their needs and demands.

The Q&A was cut short due to unexpected circumstances related to the event, not related to the presentation itself. A discussion had sprouted on technical aspects having to do with the OWL framework, and -specifically- matters focusing on the organisation of the imports (as other parties had run in issues and were interested in solution proposed by the Consortium), however it was cut short due to the aforementioned reasons.

7.5 Feedback Analysis

Given the strategies employed for the collection of feedback, it was decided to analyse and report all the gathered feedback at once, starting from a **comparative analysis** with respect to the approaches employed by comparable (in aims and scope) projects, partners close to the application level, and other stakeholders.

The vast majority of the actors **agrees on what the core issues in the domain** (relevant with respect to the activities of T2.4 and T2.5) are, but -as in the case of FATLOS- there is **no shared agreement on how to better tackle them**, nor on the specific conditions for success. Providing a connection to the feedback received in the context of the first Multidisciplinary workshop, it should be noted that the community is also divided on whether a unitary or pluralistic (situation/goal-specific) approach is preferable, though the second option is seemingly gathering attention and gaining ground even outside of OntoCommons and related projects. While this might be in part due to contingent circumstances related to the organisation of FOMI22, this should be taken as a **tentative confirmation of the approach employed by the Consortium, and/or of dissemination efficacy**.

The lack of agreement on which strategy should be pursued (given issues individuated and recognized by the entire community) emerged in some of the comments reported in §7.4. For instance, doubts were expressed on Bridge-Concepts being the "right solution", though it was recognized that they were a **pragmatic attempt at tackling the "right problem"**. Since the tools developed by WP2 are still being adjusted, and will be modified depending on the results in the implementation and testing phases, the feedback should be perceived positively: again, being pragmatic is arguably the correct stance when no tools (ideal or not) are available to deal with a recognized issue.

It is worth pointing out that various groups (among which, notably, IOF), are currently pursuing similar approaches, focusing on the creation of reference-points with respect to different vocabularies and vastly-employed golden standards, through the creation of explicit connections. In general, a renewed interest in supports for humans (within ontologies) was shown, specifically involving classes' annotations and standardisation in elucidations/definitions. This should both

provide **new chances for cooperation** (given the aims of OntoCommons) and **enable some of the tools developed** by WP2.

When it comes to the methodology employed for the alignment of TLOs, the general lack of actionable upon feedback is in line with the expectations, given the results of FATLOS. Once again, given the ambitious goals and specific characteristics of the OntoCommons project, few groups had to develop similar tools, as they did not have to face **EcoSystem-specific challenges**.

In general, the presentations reached a large community and generated (by comparison) **a good amount of reactions from the audience**, a clear sign of interest in the results of the Consortium. It should be noted that the last (and arguably more important) presentation by WP2 (the training session) was cut short due to unforeseen circumstances, and thus less time than desirable was allocated to Q&A and feedback-gathering activities in general: being the last presentation of the Workshop, contingent factors also impeded the collection of informal feedback through interactions with feedback-providers.

8. Conclusions

The objective of this deliverable was to report on WP2's activities (in the context of T2.1) related to the **collection and analysis of feedback** on the proposals and efforts of T2.4 & T2.5. Different core events were individuated; details were provided regarding the event-specific methodologies employed to collect feedback, and the analysis of the latter.

Common trends were individuated, **confirming the feedback received in occasion of the first Multidisciplinary Workshop** which played a major role in specifying the direction of the project with respect to the development of the OCES and relevant tools. This served to ensure the **adherence of OntoCommons' direction to the needs and desiderata of the target environment**.

The **feedback-loop** arguably achieved the desired effect, adjusting the targets and efforts of WP2, especially with respect to matters concerning the (internal and external) **dissemination of the results**. As a result of the feedback-gathering activities, new ways to engage with other WPs within the project and other stakeholders were individuated. While not much actionable-upon feedback was collected on the tools and methodologies proposed by T2.4 and T2.5 themselves (due to the reasons outlined in the course of the report), the comparative aspects of the activity served to avoid possible negative results due to echo chambers-effects.

Future activities will proceed following the approach outlined in the introduction, with **minor adaptations concerning the methodologies for the collection of feedback**: improvements will be made on the basis of the efficacy of the different strategies employed. In the upcoming months, more attention will be paid to the analysis of the degree of permeation of T2.4 & T2.5's outputs within the Consortium and the relevant communities, as the project reaches the required state of advancement (and the tools and methodologies proposed, the required state of maturity).